

Ben Gurion University of the Negev

Faculty of Natural Sciences

Department of Geological and Environmental Sciences

**Iron Reduction in Marine Sediments of the
Eastern Mediterranean Continental Shelf
and the Yarqon Estuary**

Thesis submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for

the Master of Sciences degree

By Omer Yorshansky

Under the supervision of Prof. Orit Sivan

January 2020

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Abstract

Ferric (Fe(III)) oxide plays a key role in the microbial respiration of organic debris in sediments, which is traditionally coupled to the reduction of electron acceptors along a distinct cascade of decreasing free energy yield. Recent studies showed, however, that different microbial respiration processes involving various electron acceptors can coexist in the same zone. In addition, in many marine sediments, including the Southeastern (SE) Mediterranean Sea continental shelf, which I have studied in this research, significant respiration by iron oxide reduction has been observed well below its expected redox zone, in the methanogenesis depth. This observations challenge our understanding of the iron cycles and other basic elements. The goal of my study was to investigate the mechanisms and related cycles of the microbial iron reduction in the methanogenic zone of diffused controlled marine sediments. I focused on two zones: (1) The upper boundary of the methanogenesis zone, in the Sulfate Methane Transition Zone (SMTZ), where anaerobic methane oxidation (AOM) by sulfate reduction is the dominant process. (2) The deep methanogenesis zone, where many marine profiles show significant unexplained Fe(II) increase and methane decrease. In the upper zone, I aimed to explore the effect of the presence of iron oxides on sulfate driven AOM and methanogenesis rates.

The research was conducted in two marine environments, which are different in their organic carbon content: The oligotrophic continental shelf of the SE Mediterranean, and the organic rich Yarqon Estuary. Porewater profiles of dissolved Fe(II), H₂S, SO₄, CH₄, dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ were performed in each location, and the SMTZ and the unexplained Fe(II) deep peaks were identified. In addition, five

incubation experiments were set up: three incubation experiments from the SE Mediterranean Sea (one from the SMTZ sediments and two from the deep methanic zone), and two incubation experiments from the Yarqon estuary (one from the shallow sulfate-rich sediments and one from the deep sulfate-depleted sediments). The incubation bottles contained slurry sediments from the desirable depth and location, together with different iron oxides, labelled ^{13}C methane and inhibitors for different processes. They were sampled for dissolved Fe(II), H_2S , SO_4 , CH_4 , dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ during 9-18 months, in order to examine the influence of the different treatments on the geochemical parameters of the pore water.

The results showed that deep iron reduction occurred in all studied locations, even if it was not observed naturally in the geochemical profiles. In addition, AOM process was observed in sediments from SE Mediterranean SMTZ, and in both shallow and deep sediments of the Yarqon estuary. The observed AOM in this study was coupled to sulfate reduction, even when sulfate concentrations were low. AOM was not observed in sediments from the deep iron reduction zone from the SE Mediterranean, probably due to the absence of sulfate in this area, which is caused by a large distance and time of diffusion, and also due to removal rates. The incubation experiments showed also that the presence of iron oxides inhibits the natural methanogenesis occurring in this zone at the SE Mediterranean and also sulfate driven AOM in the other experiments. In the Yarqon estuary sulfate reduction rate is the main factor controlling all other processes (iron reduction, methanogenesis and AOM), and only when sulfate concentration became depleted, or sulfate reduction rate decreased, the other processes were observed.

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Table of contents

1. Introduction.....	1
1.1 Microbial respiration processes.....	1
1.2 Microbial iron reduction (MIR).....	2
1.3 Sulfate methane transition zone (SMTZ).....	5
1.4 Methanogenesis, methanogens and methanotrophs	6
1.5 The link between iron reduction, AOM and methanogenesis in the methanic zone.....	7
2. Objectives.....	8
3. Methods.....	8
3.1 Study sites.....	8
3.1.1 Eastern Mediterranean Sea.....	8
3.1.2 Yarqon Estuary.....	9
3.2 Sampling and in-situ geochemical profiles.....	10
3.2.1 SE Mediterranean Sea.....	10
3.2.2 Yarqon Estuary.....	11
3.3 Analytic measurements.....	12
3.4 Quantitative PCR and 16S rRNA gene V4 amplicon pyrosequencing.....	13
3.5 Incubation experiments.....	14
3.5.1 SE Mediterranean Sea.....	14
3.5.2 Yarqon Estuary.....	17
4. Results and discussion - SE Mediterranean Sea.....	19
4.1 Porewater profiles.....	19
4.2 Incubation experiments results.....	21
4.2.1 Experiment A results.....	21
4.2.2 Experiment B results.....	24
4.2.3 Experiment C results.....	26
4.3 Discussion.....	26
4.3.1 The depth of the microbial processes in the shallow Mediterranean in SG-1 station.....	26
4.3.2 The connection between iron and sulfate driven AOM in the SMTZ.....	28
4.3.3 Deep iron reduction and related cycles.....	29
5. Results and discussion - Yarqon Estuary.....	31
5.1 Porewater profiles.....	31
5.2 Incubation experiments results.....	33
5.2.1 Incubation experiments D results.....	33
5.2.2 Incubation experiments E results.....	39

5.3 Discussion.....	42
5.3.1 The depth of the microbial processes in the Yarqon estuary.....	42
5.3.2 Iron reduction potential.....	43
5.3.3 Sulfate reduction, methanogenesis and AOM.....	43
6. Summary and conclusions.....	45
7. Supplementary.....	47
7.1 Experiment A data tables.....	47
7.2 Experiment B data tables	49
7.3 Experiment C results and data tables	49
7.4 Experiment D data tables	59
7.5 Experiment E data tables	61
8. Bibliography.....	63

List of figures

Figure 1: Traditional porewater profiles in sediments.....	2
Figure 2: schematic diagram of four possible strategies for MIR.....	3
Figure 3: Location map of the study areas.....	10
Figure 4: Piston core extraction and sampling on the Bat-Galim R.V.....	10
Figure 5: core extraction and sampling in the Yarqom estuary.....	11
Figure 6: Geochemical profiles from SG1 station from November 2017.....	19
Figure 7: Experiment A anaerobic incubation bottles.....	20
Figure 8: Experiment A results.....	22
Figure 9: Abundance of bacteria, archaea, and mcrA gene in experiment A.....	23
Figure 10: Experiment B results.....	25
Figure 11: Experiment C anaerobic incubation bottles.....	26
Figure 12: Geochemical profiles from Yarqon estuary from June 18.....	32
Figure 13: Geochemical profiles from Yarqon estuary from July 18.....	33
Figure 14: Experiment D anaerobic incubation bottles.....	34
Figure 15: Experiment D results.....	35
Figure 16: Fe(II) concentrations in experiment D.....	38
Figure 17: Sulfide concentrations in experiment D.....	39
Figure 18: Fe(II) concentrations in experiment E.....	40
Figure 19: Sulfide concentrations in experiment E.....	41
Figure 20: DIC concentrations and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ in experiment E.....	42
Figure 1S: Experiment C Fe(II) concentrations.....	55

Figure 2S: Experiment C Methane concentrations.....	56
Figure 3S: DIC concentrations and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values of experiment C.....	58

List of tables:

Table 1: Bacterial respiration processes (Jorgenson, 2000)	1
Table 2: Cores sampling details.....	12
Table 3: Details of incubation experiment A.....	15
Table 4: Details of incubation experiment B.....	16
Table 5: Details of incubation experiment C.....	17
Table 6: Details of incubation experiment D.....	18
Table 7: Details of incubation experiment E.....	19
Table 1S: Experiment A Fe(II) concentrations.....	47
Table 2S: Experiment A CH ₄ concentrations.....	47
Table 3S: Experiment A DIC concentrations.....	47
Table 4S: Experiment A $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values.....	48
Table 5S: Experiment A SO ₄ concentrations.....	48
Table 6S: Experiment A $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ values.....	48
Table 7S: Experiment A abundance of bacteria, archaea, and mcrA genes.....	48
Table 8S: Experiment B Fe(II) concentrations.....	49
Table 9S: Experiment B DIC concentrations.....	49
Table 10S: Experiment B $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values.....	49
Table 11S: Experiment C bottles distribution from different slurry incubation bottles.....	50
Table 12S: Experiment C Fe(II) concentrations.....	50
Table 13S: Experiment C DIC concentrations.....	51
Table 14S: Experiment C $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ concentrations.....	52
Table 15S: Experiment C CH ₄ concentrations.....	53
Table 16S: Experiment D Fe(II) concentrations.....	59
Table 17S: Experiment D DIC concentrations.....	59
Table 18S: Experiment D $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ concentrations.....	59
Table 19S: Experiment D CH ₄ concentrations.....	60
Table 20S: Experiment D SO ₄ concentrations.....	60
Table 21S: Experiment D sulfide concentrations.....	60
Table 22S: Experiment E Fe(II) concentrations.....	61
Table 23S: Experiment E DIC concentrations.....	61

Table 24S: Experiment E $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ concentrations.....	62
Table 25S: Experiment E sulfide concentrations.....	62

1. Introduction

1.1 Microbial respiration processes

Microbial dissimilatory processes generate energy through the decomposition of organic substrates, coupled to the reduction of electron acceptors along a cascade of decreasing free energy yield. The most known and energetically favorable dissimilatory process is the oxidation of organic carbon coupled to oxygen as terminal electron acceptor. The oxygen is consumed and become depleted within the upper few centimeters below the water-sediment interface, leading to anoxic conditions in the deeper sediment column. Under these conditions, microbial dissimilatory processes are coupled to the reduction of a series of other terminal electron acceptors besides oxygen (Froelich et al. 1979). After Oxygen, the largest free-energy yields are associated with nitrate (NO_3^-) reduction (denitrification), followed by manganese and iron oxide reduction, and then sulfate (SO_4^{2-}) reduction (Table 1).

Table 1: Anaerobic microbial respiration (Jorgensen, 2000).

Description	Reaction	ΔG^0 (KJ mol ⁻¹)
Oxic respiration	$\text{CH}_2 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	-479
Denitrification	$5\text{CH}_2\text{O} + 4\text{NO}_3^- \rightarrow 2\text{N}_2 + 4\text{HCO}_3^- + \text{CO}_2 + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	-453
Mn(IV) amorphous reduction	$\text{CH}_2\text{O} + 3\text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O} + 2\text{MnO}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{Mn}^{2+} + 4\text{HCO}_3^-$	-349
Fe(III) amorphous reduction	$\text{CH}_2\text{O} + 7\text{CO}_2 + 4\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3 \rightarrow 4\text{Fe}^{2+} + 8\text{HCO}_3^- + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	-114
Sulfate reduction	$2\text{CH}_2\text{O} + \text{SO}_4^{2-} \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{S} + 2\text{HCO}_3^-$	-77
	$4\text{H}_2 + \text{SO}_4^{2-} + \text{H}^+ \rightarrow \text{HS}^- + 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	-152
	$\text{CH}_3\text{COO}^- + \text{SO}_4^{2-} + 2\text{H}^+ \rightarrow 2\text{CO}_2 + \text{HS}^- + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	-41
Methane production	$4\text{H}_2 + \text{HCO}_3^- + \text{H}^+ \rightarrow \text{CH}_4 + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	-136
	$\text{CH}_3\text{COO}^- + \text{H}^+ \rightarrow \text{CH}_4 + \text{CO}_2$	-28

Due to the low solubility of iron and manganese minerals, and the high concentration of sulfate in the ocean (28 mM), dissimilatory bacterial sulfate reduction is responsible for the majority of organic matter oxidation in marine sediments (Jorgensen, 2000). Below the sulfate depletion depth, methane (CH_4)

production (methanogenesis) by methanogens (archaea) traditionally serves as the ultimate biological process anchoring carbon remineralization in deep sediments. However, in many aquatic sediments, significant iron oxide reduction has been observed at sediment depths that are far deeper than the expected reactive iron oxide redox zone, at the depth of methanogenesis, often accompanied by a decrease in methane concentrations (Fig. 1) (Sivan et al., 2011; Riedinger et al. 2014; Treude et al. 2014; Egger et al. 2017).

In my master I focused on this iron reduction in the methanic zone of marine sediments, and explored the couplings between iron, methane and sulfur. This is in upper methanic part, at the sulfate-methane transition zone (SMTZ) and in the “deep” methanic microbial iron reduction (MIR) zone.

Figure 1: Schematic of traditional porewater profiles in sediments due to microbial respiration with the traditional “classical” iron reduction zone, below it the sulfate reduction zone, then the sulfate-driven AOM in the SMTZ (upper grey area) and then methanogenesis. The bottom grey area illustrates the global phenomenon observed in deep sediments of increased Fe^{2+} accompanied at many sites by decreases in methane.

1.2 Microbial iron reduction (MIR)

Iron (Fe) is the fourth most abundant element in the Earth's crust. Dissimilatory iron reduction is likely one of the first evolutionary metabolisms (Lovley et al. 1998), and plays a key roles in the reductive dissolution of Fe(III) minerals in the natural environment (Weber et al. 2006), the mineralization of organic matter in freshwater sediments (Roden and Wetzel 2002), and as a redox wheel that has an important role in the geomicrobiology cycles of many elements in natural systems (Roden, 2006). Fe(III) (hydr)oxides oxidize organic compounds to CO_2 and are reduced to dissolved ferrous iron (Fe(II)) in the water (Lovley and Phillips 1988). The reduction of Fe(III) to Fe(II) is a challenge for microorganisms, because Fe(III) is present mainly in iron oxide minerals that are poorly soluble in most aqueous environments at circumneutral pH, and microbial cells are impermeable and cannot transfer solid minerals through their cell walls (Shi et al. 2007).

According to experimental observations, Fe(III)-reducing microorganisms developed different strategies to cope with the difficulty of transferring electrons from the cell to the surface of a barely soluble electron acceptor:

A. Physical contact between cell surface/cell surface compounds and ferric iron allows electron transfer from the inner membrane to the surface of the cell and then to the mineral by electron carriers such as c-type cytochromes (e.g., *Geobacter* (Mehta et al. 2005))

B. A cellular appendage (such as an electrically conductive pilus) forms a bridge between the cell and the substrate, catalyzing electron transfer. (Gorby et al. 2006; Gralnick and Newman 2007; Reguera et al. 2005)

C. Iron chelators increase the solubility of Fe(III) and hence alleviate Fe(III) reduction.

D. Electron-shuttling compounds transfer electrons from the cell to Fe(III) without the necessity of physical contact between cells and ferric iron (Gralnick and Newman 2007). A compound that act as an electron shuttles are anthraquinine-2,6-disulphonate (AQDS), which has been used as an analogue for humic acid electron shuttling (Newman & Kolter, 2000), and phenazine-1-carboxylate (PCA), which can mimic archaeal methanophanesine electron shuttling (Wang & Newman, 2008). Because the last two strategies (C and D) entail the iron oxide remaining at a distance from the cell, they may be beneficial under conditions of low mineral concentrations.

Figure 2: schematic diagram of four possible strategies that MIR have developed in order to reduce ferric iron: (A) direct contact. (B) a cellular appendage which creates a connection between the cell and the substrate to allow electron transfer. (C) a chelator that is able to bring the substrate to the cell for reduction. (D) electron shuttle that transfers the electron from the cell to the substrate which is located at a distance from the cell (Gralnick and Newman, 2007).

The reactivity of Fe(III)-oxide minerals as electron acceptors for reduction and dissolution depends on the specific surface area and structure of the mineral, the presence of Fe(II) on the surface (Fe(II) blocks active sites) and the pH (Stumm and

Sulzberger 1992). Consistent across all studies, amorphous iron (Fe(III)(OH)₃), including ferrihydrite, and goethite were shown to be more available for reduction than crystalline phases minerals as hematite (Fe₂O₃) and magnetite (Fe₃O₄) (Canfield, 1989, Lovley & Phillips, 1986; Munch & Ottow, 1983, Poulton et al., 2004). On the other hand, hematite and magnetite are excellent electron conductors - a characteristic that can enhance their reactivity for reduction (Kato et al. 2012).

Iron reduction can be related to many different reactions. First, the process of microbial iron reduction can be coupled to the oxidation of organic matter (organoclastic) or hydrogen (hydrogenotrophic) (Eq. 1) (Vargas et al., 1998).

Iron can also react with sulfurs different compounds, via the so-called "cryptic" sulfur cycle (Holmkvist et al., 2011). Ferric iron can be reduced directly by pyrite oxidation (Bottrell et al., 2000;), leading to S intermediates and followed by their disproportionation to sulfate (Eq. 2) and sulfide. The sulfide can react again with the iron oxides or precipitate as FeS or pyrite (FeS₂) and so on (Holmkvist et al., 2011; Eq. 3).

Elemental sulfur can also directly react with Fe(III) in iron-driven oxidation of elemental sulfur (Eq. 4) (Lovley and Phillips, 1994), or sulfur dis-proportionation in the presence of Fe(III) (Eq. 5) (Thamdrup et al., 1993)

Another recently discovered, type of MIR is iron reduction coupled to methane oxidation (Eq. 6) (Beal et al., 2009; Sivan et al., 2011), which will be discussed below (see section 1.5).

1.3 Sulfate methane transition zone (SMTZ)

The upper boundary of the methanogenesis zone is the SMTZ (Fig. 1), where sulfate is below 3 mM and methane is already available. In this zone, methane, which is produced in the methanogenesis zone (see section 1.4), diffuses upwards, and comes in contact with sulfate. Microbial anaerobic oxidation of methane (AOM) by sulfate reduction was found to be a dominant process in this depth (Eq. 7).

Electron transfer during sulfate-driven AOM can involve consortia of archaeal methanotrophs (ANMEs) and sulfate reducing syntrophic deltaproteobacteria (Boetius et al. 2000; Orphan et al. 2001; Basen et al. 2011). The electron transfer was suggested to occur through diffusible metabolites such as hydrogen, formate or methyl sulfides (Hoehler et al. 1994; Moran et al. 2008; Meyerdierks et al. 2010), via disproportionation (Milucka et al. 2012) or via conductive multi-heme cytochrome proteins and/or pili appendages (Mcglynn et al. 2015; Wegener et al. 2015). It was shown also that ANME-2 can perform the AOM without the sulfate reducer partner (Scheller et al., 2016), and that ANME-1 can perform both methanogenesis and methane oxidation (Beulig et al. 2019), creating "cryptic methane cycle" in the SMTZ.

The sulfate driven AOM process was found to consume up to 90% of the methane that diffuses upwards to the SMTZ (Valentine, 2002), explaining why only a small amount of methane is emitted from marine sediments (Khalil 2000), even though they contain the largest natural reservoir of methane on Earth (Archer, 2007).

Sulfate isotope fractionation during sulfate driven AOM is between 20‰ to 40‰, depending on methane concentrations and sulfate reduction rates (Deusner et al. 2014, Avrahamov et al. 2014, Sivan et al. 2014). Sulfur isotope effect during dissimilatory sulfate reduction is the result of a sequence of isotope effects intrinsic to enzymatically-catalyzed steps in the sulfate reduction cascade and of the reversibility of this process. The final isotope fractionation depends on how much back flux relative to the forward flux occurs in each single step of the overall process (Rees, 1973, Farquhar et al., 2008; Bradley et al., 2011). Recent studies in marine sediments show that other processes besides sulfate driven AOM are significant in the SMTZ. Organoclastic sulfate reduction (OSR) extends far into the SMTZ (Komada et al. 2016, Wurgaft et al. 2019) and can be responsible for up to 50% of the sulfate reduction in this zone. A study in

methane seeps (Sivan et al. 2014) showed that iron oxides stimulate sulfate-driven AOM. However, up-to-date, the involvement of iron reduction in sulfate-AOM has not been shown in non-seeps sediment (e.g. in "normal" marine sediments with diffusive profiles). In addition, the involved microorganisms have not been explored.

1.4 Methanogenesis, methanogens and methanotrophs

Methane is an important natural gas, but is also a highly effective greenhouse gas (Wuebbles & Hayhoe, 2002). Below the SMTZ, methane is produced by two main pathways, depending on the environment. In freshwater sediments acetoclastic methanogenesis is the dominant pathway (Eq. 8), while in marine sediments the dominant pathway is hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis (Eq.9) (Whiticaret al. 1986)

Carbon isotopes can provide good indication on the methanogenesis process, depth distribution and location of the AOM process (Whiticar, 1999) Usually during methanogenesis there is a large discrimination against ^{13}C , where the methane produced is isotopically light (between -50‰ to -100‰) and the residual dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) pool is heavier by 50-70‰. When outward diffusing methane comes in contact with an electron acceptor it can be consumed by microbial oxidation (methanotrophy). The methanotrophs, which consume methane, and methanogens, which produce methane, were found also to be linked, using similar mechanism in reverse mode (Hoehler et al., 1994; Orcutt et al., 2005; Orcutt & Meile, 2008).

In anoxic marine sediments AOM is coupled mainly to sulfate reduction (Hoehler et al., 1994), as mentioned above. This process leads to carbon isotope fractionation of 0-10‰ (Alperin et al., 1988; Martens et al., 1999), producing DIC that has close carbon isotope composition of its methane precursor.

Other types of AOM have been observed too as AOM by nitrite or nitrate (Haroon et al., 2013; Shen et al., 2017; Ettwig et al. 2010), AOM by humic acids (Blodau and Deppe, 2012) or AOM by metals (Beal et al., 2009, Ettwig et al. 2016; Yan et al., 2018; Cai et al., 2018). Iron driven AOM (Eq. 6) has also been observed in limited studies. The potential for iron-coupled AOM in marine environments was shown by Beal et al. (2009) in microcosm experiments with methane marine seep sediments. Iron-coupled

AOM in regular (non-seep) marine sedimentary profiles has previously been proposed mainly through the modeling of geochemical profiles in deep sea sediments (Sivan et al. 2007; Riedinger et al. 2014) and in brackish coastal sediments (Slomp et al. 2013; Segarra et al. 2013; Egger et al. 2016).

1.5 The link between iron reduction, AOM and methanogenesis in the methanic zone

In the deep methanogenesis zone, many aquatic profiles show significant unexplained Fe(II) increase. A few possible pathways can be related to this increase:

- 1) Inhibition of methanogenesis, under iron-reducing conditions, due to competition between methanogens and iron-reducing bacteria for the common substrates acetate and hydrogen (Conrad 1999; Lovley and Phillips 1986; Roden 2003). The inhibitory effect of Fe reduction on methanogenesis thus appears to be lower for crystalline Fe oxides such as hematite and magnetite, which are less bioavailable to Fe reducing organisms than poorly crystalline (amorphous) Fe (oxyhydr) oxides (e.g. ferrihydrite and lepidocrocite) (Lovley, 1991; Qu et al., 2004; Zhuang et al., 2015)
- 2) Methanogens switch from methanogenesis to iron reduction. Methanogens were previously shown to reduce iron in pure cultures close to natural conditions (Bodegom et al., 2004; Bond et al., 2002; Yamada et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2013 Sivan et al. 2016) and also in lake sediments (Bar-Or et al. 2017).
- 3) Iron driven AOM. Evidences from lake sediments show that there is iron driven AOM in the deep methanogenesis zone (Bar-Or et al. 2017). Deep iron driven AOM was suggested also in diffusive marine profiles, but based mainly on models (Sivan et al 2007; Treude et al. 2014; Riedinger et al. 2014; Egger et al. 2017). The potential free energy yield which was calculated for the process of Fe-AOM with Amorphous iron ($\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$) (Eq.6) is between -150 to -170 kJ mol⁻¹ (Riedinger et al. 2014). Compared to the -28 kJ mol⁻¹ free energy yield of methanogenesis (Jørgensen et al. 2000), the iron driven AOM can be profitable for microbial respiration and can explain the transition between the processes in suitable environments.
- 4) Cryptic cycle between iron and sulfur that reactivates the iron oxides and stimulates both iron and sulfate reduction by methane (Holmkvist, et al. 2011; Treude et al. 2014; Egger et al. 2017).

2. Objectives

The primary goal of this study was to characterize the link between iron reduction processes in marine methanic sediments to sulfur and carbon. I focused on two zones:

(1) The upper boundary of the methanogenesis zone, in the SMTZ, where microbial anaerobic methane oxidation (AOM) by sulfate reduction is the dominate process.

(2) The deep methanogenesis zone, where many marine profiles show significant unexplained Fe(II) increase and methane decrease.

The research was conducted in two different marine environments: The continental shelf of the south eastern (SE) Mediterranean, and the Yarqon estuary. This is in order to test the above in environments with different organic carbon content (low and high, respectively).

Specific goals

1. Identify the SMTZ and deep iron reduction in both study sites.
2. Investigate the mechanisms of the iron reduction process in the SMTZ and in the deep methanic layer (sulfur cycle? methane cycle? methanogens? methanotrophs?).
3. Explore the effect of the presence of iron oxides in the SMTZ on sulfate driven AOM and methanogenesis rates (does iron presence stimulate sulfate reduction? is there a competition between the processes?).

3. Method

3.1 Study sites

3.1.1 SE Mediterranean Sea

The continental shelf margin of Israel is built mainly of Pliocene-Quaternary Nile-derived sediments. The sediments are mostly clay silts between 30-50 m, while the clay fraction dominates at >50 m water (Nir 1984; Sandler and Herut 2000). Along the shelf the carbonate fraction increases northward (7-15 wt.%) and onshore due to the decrease in Nile derived sediment and higher local calcium carbonate biogenic fragments (Y. Nir, 1984; Goldsmith et al., 2001). The organic carbon content in the sediments is less than 1%. The bottom water temperature is ~17 to 22 °C.

Sulfate concentration in the water-sediment interface is ~30 mM (Sela-Adler et al., 2015), and typically is not consumed because of the oligotrophic nature of the Mediterranean Sea. This research was taken place in SG-1 station in the shallow (85m water depth) South Eastern (SE) Mediterranean Sea (Fig. 3). This study site was chosen due to a gas front that was discovered in the continental shelf of northern Israel at water depth of 37-112 m (Schattner et al., 2012), and that is why in this site the sulfate is being consumed completely by 200 cm depth. Sela-Adler et al. (2015) concluded that the methane found in the Mediterranean continental shelf is biogenic. Biogenic methanogenesis becomes the dominant process when sulfate is no longer detected. It has been established also that sulfate driven AOM occurs in the Mediterranean continental shelf. Wurgaft et al. 2019 showed that within the SMTZ, both sulfate driven AOM and OSR occurs, accounted for about half of the total sulfate reduction. At ~400 cm and ~600 cm ferrous iron is at maximum concentration and suggests that iron oxides are available for reduction below the traditional depth (preliminary results).

3.1.2 Yarqon Estuary

The Yarqon (Figure 3) is the largest coastal river in Israel with length of 27.5 km and a drainage basin area of 1800 km². As other streams along the Mediterranean coast of Israel, the bottom bathymetry of the downstream lies below sea level, enabling the intrusion of seawater and the formation of highly stratified estuary up to a few kilometers inland. The estuary contains high organic carbon loads from upstream (20-60 mg L⁻¹; Arnon et al., 2015) and lower water mass close to seawater salinity (~19000 mg Cl⁻). in the Yarqon sediments, the upper 10 cm are dominated by organo-clastic sulfate reduction and sulfate-driven AOM is the dominant process below (Antler et al. 2014). Methanogenesis and sulfate reduction can co-exist while the microbes share substrates (Sela-Adler et al., 2017), and the methanogenesis rates are two orders of magnitude lower than rates of sulfate reduction.

Figure 3: Location map of the studied areas. SG-1 station is located in 85 meters water depth in the SE Mediterranean Sea ($32^{\circ} 57' 50.9394''$ N $34^{\circ} 55' 16.0062''$ E), and the Yarqon Estuary is located in Tel Aviv ($32^{\circ} 06.0792'$ N; $34^{\circ} 48. 3633'$ E), 3 km upstream of the coast.

3.2 Sampling and in-situ geochemical profiles

3.2.1 SE Mediterranean Sea

Eight meters long sediment core was collected in November 2017 by the new R.V. Bat Galim (Fig. 4) from SG-1 station (Table 2), Mediterranean continental shelf of Israel from undisturbed seafloor sediments at water depths around 85 m by a Benthos 2175 piston corer. For one of the experiments sediment from six meters long sediment core which was collected and analyzed similarly in January 2017 was used. The sediment core was sliced on board every 30-50 cm within minutes of the core extraction from the seafloor. While slicing, about 1.5 ml from the edge of each fresh sediment slice was transferred immediately into N_2 -flushed crimp bottles containing 5 ml of 1.5 N NaOH for the headspace measurements of CH_4 . About another 1.5 ml sediment was transferred into glass vials for porosity measurement.

Figure 4: Piston core sampling and slicing on the R/V Bat-Galim

Subsamples from the edge of each sediment slice was stored in 50 ml vials under anaerobic conditions for pore water extracted which was conducted within 24 hours by centrifugation at 27,000 g at 4°C under a N₂ atmosphere. The supernatant was filtered through 0.22 µm filters for the measurements of Fe(II), Fe(tot), sulfide, sulfate, major ions, DIC and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ (detailed in section 3.3).

3.2.2 Yarqon Estuary

Two approximately 40 cm long sediment cores were collected in the Yarqon estuary, 3 km upstream (Fig. 5), using a gravity corer in June 2018 and July 2018 (Table 2). The cores were kept in the dark and treated within a day of sampling. They were sectioned into slices of 1–2 cm thickness under a nitrogen atmosphere to prevent oxidation. While slicing, about 1.5 ml from of each sediment slice was transferred immediately into N₂-flushed crimp bottles containing 5 ml of 1.5 N NaOH for the headspace measurements of CH₄. About another 1.5 ml sediment was transferred into glass vials for porosity measurement. The rest of the sediment slices were transferred into 50 ml vials under anaerobic conditions for pore water extracted by centrifugation at 27,000 g at 4°C under a N₂ atmosphere. The supernatant was filtered through 0.22µm filters for the measurements of Fe(II), sulfide, sulfate, DIC and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ (detailed in section 3.3).

Figure 5: Core extraction and sampling in the Yarqon estuary

Table 2: Cores sampling details.

Site	date	Longitude	Latitude	Water depth
SE Mediterranean Sea SG1	November 2017	32° 57' 50.9394" N	34° 55' 16.0062" E	87 m
	January 2017			
Yarqon Estuary	June 2018	32° 06.0792' N	34° 48. 3633' E	1.5-2 m
	July 2018			

3.3 Analytic measurements

The same analytic techniques were used for the Eastern Mediterranean continental Shelf, the Yarqon estuary and the incubation experiments.

Methane

About 100 μl was taken for the methane concentration in profiles and slurry experiments with a gas tight syringe from the headspace of each bottle after it has been vigorously shaken. Headspace methane concentrations were measured on a Thermo Scientific gas chromatograph (GC) equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID) at a precision of 2 $\mu\text{mol/L}$.

Ferrous iron

Fe^{2+} was measured using the ferrozine method (Stookey, 1970). 1 ml of filtered pore water/slurry experiment sample was inserted to 15 ml falcon tube with 100 μl of ferrozine (Stookey 1970). The samples were measured in Spectroquant Pharo 100 spectrophotometer from Merck at 562 nm wavelength, with an error of less than 7 $\mu\text{mol/L}$.

Hydrogen sulfide

Sulfide was measured using Cline method (Cline, 1969). 1.5 ml of filtered pore water was inserted to 15 ml falcon tube with 0.1 ml of ZnAc 200 gr/L. Then 120 μL of the diamine reagent was added into the solution, the sample was placed in a dark place for 30 minutes before measuring. Sulfide was measured Spectroquant Pharo 100 spectrophotometer from Merck at 665 nm wavelength, with the precision of ± 1 $\mu\text{mol/L}$.

DIC and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$

The DIC and the $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ concentrations were measured by inserting approximately 0.25 ml of the sample to a sealed glass vial with two drops of phosphoric acid and He atmosphere, this is in order to transform all the inorganic carbon species to CO_2 , which was released to the headspace of the vial. The CO_2 isotopic values were measured in a Focus (Thermo) GC-IRMS with the precision of $\pm 0.1\%$. The CO_2 concentration was calculated from the peaks of the isotopic measurement with precision of $\pm 0.1 \text{ mmol L}^{-1}$.

Sulfate and $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$

Sulfate concentrations were measured in HPLC (High Pressure Liquid Chromatography) with the precision of $\pm 0.25 \text{ mM}$. About 100 μl water sample was flushed by N_2 , in order to remove sulfides, and then diluted by 9.9 ml of DDW. For $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ analysis, $\sim 1 \text{ ml}$ of sample was transferred into a vial with same amount of 200gr/L ZnAc to remove the sulfides oxidation, and Ba was added in order to react with the sulfate and create barite mineral. The barite was combusted at 1030°C in a Flash Element Analyzer (EA), and the resulting sulfur dioxide (SO_2) was measured by continuous helium flow on a GS-IRMS (Thermo Finnegan Delta V Plus Godwin Laboratory, University of Cambridge).

Porosity

Sediment samples were stored in a glass vial and kept in 60° oven for one week until stable weight was achieved. The vials were weighted before and after the heating.

3.4 Quantitative PCR and 16S rRNA gene V4 amplicon

pyrosequencing

All biological lab work was conducted at Shanghai Jiao Tong University, School of Life Sciences and Biotechnology in professor Fengping Wang lab, as part of a collaboration between professor Orit Sivan lab and professor Fengping Wang lab. DNA was extracted from experiment A sediment samples using Power Soil DNA Kit (MoBio Laboratories, Inc., Carlsbad, CA, USA) following manufacturer's instructions. Copy numbers of selected genes were estimated with quantitative PCR (qPCR) as described previously (Niu et al., 2017) using specific primers: Uni519f/Arc908R and bac341f/519r for archaeal and bacterial 16S rRNA genes, respectively, and mlas/mcrA-rev for the mcrA gene, which encodes the α -subunit of

methyl-coenzyme M reductase. The amplification efficiency was 92.4%, 105.3% and 94.2% for the archaeal 16S rRNA, bacterial 16S rRNA and the *mcrA* gene, respectively (the respective R^2 of the standard curve was 0.996, 0.998 and 0.991).

The V4 regions of bacterial and archaeal 16S rRNA genes were amplified using barcoded 515FB/806RB primers (Walters et al., 2015) and Arch519/Arch806 primers (Song et al., 2013), respectively. PCR mixture contained 6 – 10 ng total DNA, 5 μ L 10 \times Ex Taq buffer, 4 μ L 2.5 mmol L⁻¹ dNTP mix, 1 μ L of each primer, 0.25 μ L Ex Taq polymerase (Ex-Taq; TaKaRa, Dalian, China) and 5 μ L bovine serum albumin (25 mg mL⁻¹) in a total volume of 50 μ L

3.5 Incubation experiments

3.5.1 SE Mediterranean Sea

Three Incubation experiments were performed in sediments from the SE Mediterranean
Experiment A:

In order to explore the effect of the presence of iron oxides in the SMTZ on sulfate driven AOM, slurry from the SMTZ from January 2017 was divided into 60 ml sterilized crimp-top glass bottles. Before the experiment set up, the slurry was incubated for 9 months in anaerobic sterilized crimp-top glass bottles, with 1:1 sediment to artificial seawater (with 10 mM Sulfate) ratio in order to enrich the bacterial population. The slurry was divided then into 8 bottles, with final sediment to artificial seawater ratio of 1:3. Each two duplicate bottles had different treatment (Table 3). Two ml of methane were added to the head space of all bottles and 0.5 ml labeled methane (¹³CH₄) was added to most of them (except for two bottles with the addition of labeled bicarbonate (H¹³CO₃⁻). Labeled methane was added in order to follow the transformation from labeled ¹³C-methane to ¹³C-DIC, as a direct evidence for methane oxidation. After 11 months 1.35 ml of methane and 0.15 ml of labeled methane were added to all bottles. Labeled bicarbonate was added to two bottles in order to follow the transformation from light methane to less enriched DIC, or the opposite reaction-labeled ¹³C-DIC to ¹³C-methane, as a direct evidence for methane oxidation or methanogenesis. In order to examine the influence of iron presence on sulfate reduction, hematite (Fe₂O₃) was added to most bottles (except two natural control) in 3 stages of the experiment: 12 mM in the initial experiment set up, 5 more mM after 5 months, and 5 mM after 14 months with the addition of Sodium molybdate (see below). Two of the

bottles were sterilized by autoclave for control. The pore water in the bottles were analyzed for Fe(II), SO_4 , $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$, CH_4 , DIC and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$, along 18 months (detailed in section 3.3). After 14 months, 16 ml of artificial seawater and Sodium molybdate (Na_2MoO_4) (final concentration of 1 mM), sulfate reduction and sulfur disproportionation inhibitor (Banat & Nedwell, 1984), were added to most bottles (except for the two bottles with the addition of labeled bicarbonate) in order to examine the influence of sulfate reduction inhibition on AOM. Sediment samples from each bottle were taken for qPCR analysis before the molybdate addition.

Table 3: Details of incubation experiment A

	Methane	labeled methane	labeled bicarbonate	Hematite
A1+A2	2 ml	0.5 ml		12 mM
A3+A4	2 ml	0.5 ml		12 mM
A5+A6	2 ml		10 mM	
A7+A8(killed)	2 ml	0.5 ml		12 mM

Experiment B:

In order to investigate the connection between iron and methanogenesis, slurry from the deep methanogenesis iron rich zone from November 2017 was divided into 60 ml sterilized crimp-top glass bottles. Before the experiment set up, the slurry was incubated for 3 months in anaerobic sterilized crimp-top glass bottles, with 1:1 sediment to artificial seawater (without sulfate) ratio in order to enrich the bacterial population. The slurry was divided into 8 bottles, with final sediment to artificial seawater ratio of 1:3. Each two duplicate bottles had different treatment (Table 4). About 0.5 ml of labeled methane was added to all bottles in order to follow methane oxidation. Amorphous iron ($\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$) was added to most bottles (except two natural control) to a final concentration of 10 mM, in order to examine the influence of iron presence on methanogenesis. BES (2-bromoethanesulfonate), a specific inhibitor for methanogens (inhibits the last step of methanogenesis and the first step of methanotrophy) (Zehnder & Brock, 1979), was added to two bottles+ two killed control. Two of the bottles were sterilized by autoclave for control. The pore water in the bottles were analyzed for Fe(II), DIC and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$, along 16 months (detailed in section 3.3).

Table 4: Details of incubation experiment B

	Labeled methane	BES	Amorphous iron
B1+B2	0.5 ml		
B3+B4	0.5 ml		10 mM
B5+B6	0.5 ml	30 mM	10 mM
B7+A8 (killed)	0.5 ml	30 mM	10 mM

Experiment C:

In order to investigate the mechanism and other related cycles and microbes of the iron reduction process, slurry from the deep methanogenesis iron rich zone from November 2017 was divided into 60 ml sterilized crimp-top glass bottles. Before the experiment set up, the slurry was incubated for 4 months in anaerobic sterilized crimp-top glass bottles, with 1:1 sediment to artificial seawater (without Sulfate) ratio in order to enrich the bacterial population. The slurry was divided into 38 bottles, with final sediment to artificial seawater ratio of 1:3. Each two duplicate bottles had different treatment (Table 5). About 1.35 ml of methane and 0.15 ml of labeled methane were added to all bottles. Three types of iron oxides: magnetite (Fe_3O_4) hematite (Fe_2O_3) and amorphous iron ($\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$) was added to part of the bottles in order to examine the influence of different iron oxides with different solubility and energy yield on iron reduction. Two different methanogens inhibitors: BES and acetylene (Sportt et al. 1982) were used as methanogenesis inhibitors, in order to examine the influence of methanogens on iron reduction. Sodium molybdate was added as sulfate reduction and sulfur disproportionation inhibitor, in order to examine the influence of the sulfur cycle on iron reduction. AQDS (andanthraquinone-2,6-disulfonate) was added as electron shuttle analogs (Newman & Kolter, 2000) in order to examine electron shuttling mechanism influence on iron reduction. Ten of the bottles with different treatments were sterilized by autoclave for control. The pore water in the bottles were analyzed for Fe(II), CH_4 , DIC and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ along a full year (detailed in section 3.3).

Table 5: Details of incubation experiment C

	Methane+ labeled methane	Hematite	Amorphous iron	BES	Acetylene	Sodium molybdate	magnetite	AQDS
C1+C2+ C37	1.5 ml							
C3+C4+ C38	1.5 ml	12 mM						
C5+C6	1.5 ml	12 mM		30 mM				
C7+C8	1.5 ml	12 mM				1 mM		
C9+C10	1.5 ml	12 mM					12 mM	
C11+C12	1.5 ml	12 mM			0.1 % HS			
C13+C14+ C19+C20	1.5 ml		12 mM					
C15+C16	1.5 ml		12 mM	30 mM				
C17+C18	1.5 ml		12 mM			1 mM		
C21+C22	1.5 ml		12 mM		0.1 % HS			
C23+C24	1.5 ml		12 mM					1 mM
C25+C26 (killed)	1.5 ml		12 mM		0.1 % HS			
C27+C28 (killed)	1.5 ml	12 mM		30 mM				
C29+C30 (killed)	1.5 ml	12 mM			0.1 % HS			
C31+C32 (killed)	1.5 ml	12 mM	12 mM			1 mM		
C33+C34 (killed)	1.5 ml		12 mM					
C35+C36 (killed)	1.5 ml		12 mM					1 mM

3.5.2 Yarqon Estuary

Two Incubation experiments were performed in sediments from the Yarqon estuary

Experiment D:

In order to explore the effect of the presence of iron oxides on sulfate driven AOM in estuarine sediments with high concentration of sulfate in the porewater, slurry from the Yarqon estuary from June 2018 was divided into 120 ml sterilized crimp-top glass bottles. The slurry was divided into 10 bottles, with final sediment to artificial seawater ratio of 1:2. Each two duplicate bottles had different treatment (Table 6). About 2.5 ml of methane and 0.25 ml of labeled methane were added to all bottles. Two types of iron oxides: hematite and amorphous iron were added to part of the bottles in order to examine the influence of different iron oxides with different solubility and energy yield on iron reduction, sulfate reduction, AOM and methanogenesis. Two bottles were added with Sodium molybdate as sulfate reduction and sulfur disproportionation inhibitor in addition to Hematite in order to examine the iron reduction potential when

sulfate reduction is inhibited. Two of the bottles were sterilized by autoclave for control. The pore water in the bottles were analyzed for Fe(II), SO₄, CH₄, DIC and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$, along one year (detailed in section 3.3).

Table 6: Details of incubation experiment D

	Methane+ labeled methane	Hematite	Amorphous iron	Sodium molybdate
D1+D2	2.5 ml			
D3+CD4	2.5 ml	10 mM		
D5+D6	2.5 ml		10 mM	
D7+D8	2.5 ml	10 mM		1 mM
D9 (killed)	2.5 ml	10 mM		1 mM
D10 (killed)	2.5 ml		10 mM	1 mM

Experiment E:

In order to explore the effect of the presence of iron oxides on the deep methanogenesis zone in estuarine sediments, with seawater salinity, slurry from the sulfate depleted zone of the Yaron estuary from July 2018 was divided into 120 ml sterilized crimp-top glass bottles. Before the experiment set up, the slurry was incubated for 3 months in anaerobic sterilized crimp-top glass bottles, with 1:1 sediment to artificial seawater (without Sulfate) ratio in order to enrich the bacterial population. The slurry was divided into 19 bottles, with final sediment to artificial seawater ratio of 1:2. Each two duplicate bottles had different treatment (Table 7). About 5 ml of methane and 0.5 ml of labeled methane were added to all bottles. Three types of iron oxides: magnetite, hematite and amorphous iron were added to part of the bottles in order to examine the influence of different iron oxides with different solubility and energy yield on iron reduction, sulfate reduction, AOM and methanogenesis. Two bottles were added only Sodium molybdate as sulfate reduction and sulfur disproportionation inhibitor, and two bottles were added Sodium molybdate in addition to magnetite in order to examine the iron reduction potential when sulfate reduction is inhibited. BES was added to two bottles as methanogenesis inhibitor in addition to magnetite in order to examine the influence of methanogens on iron reduction. Three of the bottles were sterilized by autoclave for control. The pore water in the bottles were analyzed for Fe(II), SO₄, DIC and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$, along 9 months (detailed in section 3.3).

Table 7: Details of incubation experiment E

	Methane+ labeled methane	Hematite	Amorphous iron	magnetite	Sodium molybdate	BES
E1+E2+E3+E 4	5.5 ml					
E5+E6	5.5 ml				1 mM	
E7+E8	5.5 ml	10 mM				
E9+E10	5.5 ml			10 mM	1 mM	
E11+E12	5.5 ml			10 mM		30 mM
E13+E14	5.5 ml			10 mM	1 mM	
E15+E16	5.5 ml		10 mM			
E17	5.5 ml		10 mM		1 mM	
E18	5.5 ml			10 mM	1 mM	
E19	5.5 ml			10 mM		30 mM

4. Results and discussion - SE Mediterranean Sea

4.1 Porewater profiles results

Geochemical profiles (Fig. 6) from SG-1 station, sampled in November 2017, were performed in order to quantify the anaerobic respiration processes occurring in the Mediterranean continental shelf sediments, and to identify the sediment zone, which is relevant for incubation experiments. It should be noted again that these cores were collected at locations where gas layer was shown to exist below, based on geophysical observations (Sela-Adler et al., 2015).

DIC concentration (Fig. 6A) showed maximum of ~90 mM at 180-240 cm depth. This value is relatively high in comparison to the previous profiles, and can be related to technical problems with the measurement. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values (Fig. 6B) decreased from -14.4‰ at 30 cm depth to minimum of -15.7‰ at 180 cm depth, then increased again to -14.7‰ at 370 cm, decreased again to -15.8‰ at 370 cm, and finally increased again to -14.9‰ at 820 cm depth. The porosity (Fig. 6F) decreased slightly from 0.5 at the top of the core to 0.4 at the bottom of the core. The methane profile (Fig. 6C) showed an increase in methane concentration immediately after the consumption of sulfate (Fig. 6D), with maximum concentration of 2.6 mM at 670 and 430 cm depth. Sulfate was found to be depleted sharply at 180 cm below sea floor depth (Fig. 6D). Sulfide concentrations were below the detection limit (~1 μM), probably due to precipitation with iron. Fe(II) concentrations (Fig. 6E) increased to 14.4 μM at 270 cm, then decreased to 3.5 μM at 340 cm, increased again to 34.5 μM at 340 cm, decreased to 3.2

μM at 510 cm, and finally increased again to $27.9 \mu\text{M}$ at 600 cm depth and decreased to $1.2 \mu\text{M}$ at 820 cm depth.

Figure 6: Geochemical profiles from SG1 station from November 2017. A-DIC concentrations. B- $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values. C-Methane concentrations. D-Sulfate concentrations. E-Fe(II) concentrations. F-Sediment porosity. The SMTZ appears to be at 180 cm depth according to sulfate, methane and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values. Location of the sediments which were taken to bacterial enrichments incubations and experiments are marked in red.

According to these profiles, two depths were chosen to perform slurry bacterial enrichment incubations and experiments: 1) The SMTZ, at 180-205 cm bsf depth (according to minimum sulfate concentration, increase in methane concentration, and minimum in $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values); 2) Fe(II) maximum zone, at 400-435 cm bsf depth

4.2 Incubation experiments results

4.2.1 Experiment A:

Experiment A (Fig. 7) was set up with 22 grams of 1:1 water to sediment ratio (sediment slurry from the SMTZ of January 2017 sampling, see section 3.5.1), and 22 grams of artificial sea water with 10 mM sulfate to final water to sediment ratio of 3:1. In this experiment, I quantified the iron reduction processes

Figure 7: Experiment A anaerobic incubation bottles.

and their link to sulfate-driven AOM in this zone. The incubations thus included additions of hematite, labeled methane, labeled bicarbonate, and molybdate, compared to live natural and two sterilized by autoclave control incubations.

The Fe(II) concentrations (Fig. 8A) in bottles containing hematite increased in the first four days to $\sim 55 \mu\text{M}$, while natural bottles increased only to $\sim 40 \mu\text{M}$ during that time and reached $\sim 50 \mu\text{M}$ after 18 days. There was a decrease to $\sim 50 \mu\text{M}$ after 60 days in the bottles containing hematite. All bottles (including the dead control) showed $\sim 5 \mu\text{M}$ variation in Fe(II) concentration between 60 to 440 days.

Methane initial amount was between 0.05 to 0.07 mmol in head space (Fig. 8B). The results do not show a distinct trend in the methane concentration, and all bottles show small decrease or increase within the initial concentration range. Dead control final methane amount after 320 days was 0.07 mmol in head space, while the non-killed bottles final amount was between 0.04 to 0.06 mmol in head space.

DIC initial concentration in all bottles was $\sim 7.5 \text{ mM}$ (Fig. 8C). The concentration decreased gradually in all bottles to $\sim 6 \text{ mM}$ final concentration after 440 days.

The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ initial value of non-killed bottles was $\sim 16\text{‰}$ (Fig. 8D). In bottles containing hematite, $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ value increased to 44.3‰ and 18.5‰ final value after 440 days, while natural control bottles $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ value increased to 65.1‰ and 50.6‰ final value after 440 days. Dead control bottles showed values between -4‰ to -10.5‰ along the experiment.

After 475 days, the bottles were diluted with artificial sea water and molybdate was added (see section 3.5.1) in order to ensure the involvement of sulfate in AOM in all bottles. After this addition, natural bottles $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ value decreased to 55.2‰ and 44.1‰, and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ value in bottles containing hematite decreased to 37.5‰. Both natural bottles and bottles containing hematite kept a relatively stable value with 5‰ variation for 3 more months until the end of the experiment. $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ of the labeled bicarbonate initial values was 1653‰ and 1467‰, and this value decreased in 440 days to 1290‰ and 1159‰ respectively.

Figure 8: Experiment A results. Black arrow indicates hematite, molybdate and artificial sea water addition after 475 days. A-Fe(II) concentrations. B-Methane concentration in head space. C-DIC concentrations. D- $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values. E-Sulfate concentrations. F- $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ values.

Sulfate initial concentration was between 7.8 to 8.5 mM (Fig. 8E). The results do not show a distinct trend in the sulfate concentration. The $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ initial value of bottles containing hematite was 5.4‰, and increased to 7‰ and 7.5‰ in 440 days. The $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$

initial values of natural control bottles was 5.3‰, and increase to 8.1‰, the highest value of all bottles, in 440 days. The initial value of dead control bottles was 5.6‰, and this value remained stable with 0.1‰ change along the experiment.

The qPCR of bacterial and archaeal 16S rRNA genes revealed that in sediments, which were taken in the beginning of the experiment, the abundance of bacteria was 8.4×10^6 copies per g wet sediment (Fig. 9A), while the abundance of archaea was 11×10^6 copies per g wet sediment. The abundance in sediment, which was taken from bottles containing hematite after 440 days of incubation was similar to the beginning for bacteria (9.5×10^6 and 13.3×10^6 copies per g wet sediment), and doubled from time zero sediments for archaea (21.6×10^6 and 26.1×10^6 copies per g wet sediment). In the sediment, which was taken from the natural control bottles after 440 days of incubation the abundance was significantly enriched compared to the beginning (31.6×10^6 and 25.7×10^6 copies per g wet sediment for bacteria, and 54.7×10^6 and 49.1×10^6 copies per g wet sediment for archaea).

Figure 9: Abundance of bacteria, archaea, and mcrA gene in experiment A. A-Large scale of Gene copy number per wet sediment presenting all genes. B-Small scale presenting only mcrA gene.

The abundance of the mcrA gene in sediment from the beginning was 0.33×10^6 copies per g wet sediment (Fig. 9B). The abundance of the mcrA gene in sediment which were taken from bottles containing hematite after 440 days of incubation was similar to abundance in sediment from the beginning (0.36×10^6 and 0.74×10^6 copies

per g wet sediment), while in sediments, which were taken from the natural control bottles after 440 days of incubation, the abundance was one order above the abundance in sediment from the beginning (2×10^6 and 1.6×10^6 copies per g wet sediment).

4.2.2 Experiment B:

Experiment B was set up with sediment slurry from the deep methanic zone (400-435 cm depth) from November 2017 sampling. The slurry was made from 20 grams of 1:1 water to sediment ratio (which was incubated for 4 months from sampling time to the experiment setup), and 20 grams of artificial sea water with no sulfate to final water to sediment ratio of 3:1. In this experiment I examined the possible connection between iron reduction and methanogenesis, methanogens or methanotrophs, by the addition of amorphous iron, BES, labeled methane, for 490 days and the results are presented in figure 10.

Fe(II) concentrations (Fig.10C) in bottles with amorphous iron addition increased in the first nine days from $\sim 87 \mu\text{M}$ to $130 \mu\text{M}$, while natural bottles increased from $\sim 110 \mu\text{M}$ to $140 \mu\text{M}$ in the first nine days. After 18 days Fe(II) concentrations in natural bottles and bottles containing amorphous iron decreased in $\sim 20 \mu\text{M}$, and increased again after 280 days to $\sim 150 \mu\text{M}$ in natural bottles, and to $\sim 130 \mu\text{M}$ in bottles containing amorphous iron. The Fe(II) concentrations in bottles with both BES and amorphous iron increased in the first nine days from $80 \mu\text{M}$ and $95 \mu\text{M}$ to $\sim 160 \mu\text{M}$, then decreased to $\sim 110 \mu\text{M}$ and $\sim 124 \mu\text{M}$ after 18 days, and finally increased again to a final concentration of $\sim 250 \mu\text{M}$ after 490 days. Dead control bottles (with both BES and amorphous iron) increased in the first nine days from $\sim 95 \mu\text{M}$ to $\sim 175 \mu\text{M}$, then decreased to $\sim 95 \mu\text{M}$ after 30 days, and finally increased again to a final concentration of $\sim 160 \mu\text{M}$ after 490 days.

DIC initial concentration in all non-killed bottles was ~6 mM, and ~10 mM in autoclaved bottles (Fig. 10B). Concentration in all bottles showed 1-2 mM decrease within the first month, until the non-killed bottles reached a stable value of ~5 mM, and autoclaved bottles reached a stable value of ~9.5 mM after one month. Concentrations in natural bottles and bottles containing amorphous iron increased gradually and reached a final concentration of ~5.9 mM after 490 days, while bottles containing BES reached to ~7.2 mM final concentration. Dead control bottles concentrations decreased to 8.5 mM final concentration after 490 days.

The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ initial value in all bottles was between 7.8‰ to 11‰ (Fig. 10A). Dead control bottles and bottles containing amorphous iron kept a stable $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values with 1‰ variation for 490 days. Autoclaved bottles final value was ~8.5‰ and bottles containing amorphous iron final value were 9.8‰ and 9.1‰. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ value in bottles containing BES decreased gradually to a final value of ~-17.8‰. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$

value in natural bottles was stable for the first 165 days, and then increased to final value of -5.9‰ and -2.9‰.

4.2.3 Experiment C results

Experiment C (Fig. 11) was set up with sediment slurry from the deep methanic zone (400-435 cm depth) during November 2017 sampling. The slurry was made from 20 grams of 1:1 water to sediment ratio (which was incubated for 5 months from sampling time to the experiment setup), and 20 grams of artificial sea water with no sulfate to final water to sediment ratio of 3:1.

Figure 11: Experiment C anaerobic incubation bottles.

In this experiment, I investigate the mechanism and other related cycles and microbes of the iron reduction process. The slurry was amended with hematite, magnetite, amorphous iron, BES, acetylene, molybdate, AQDS and labeled methane. The results of this experiment did not show a specific trend during the one-year incubation. All experiment C results are detailed in the supplementary data.

4.3 Discussion

4.3.1 The depth of the microbial processes in the shallow

Mediterranean in SG-1 station

In the core which was collected from SG-1 station in the Mediterranean continental shelf in November 2017, the SMTZ appeared to be at 170-210 cm depth, according to the increase in methane concentration right below the depth where sulfate has been exhausted, together with a minimum in $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ (Fig. 6). Previous studies in SG1 (Sela-Adler et al. 2015, Wurgaft et al. 2019) showed similar trends in sulfate, methane DIC and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$. The depth of SMTZ observed by Sela-Adler et al. (2015), however, was approximately 0–50 cm, and in Wurgaft et al., 2019 between 100 to 270 cm in September 2015 and between 80 to 210 cm in January 2017, suggesting high spatial heterogeneity of the geochemical properties of the pore water. Wurgaft et al. (2019) calculated results from pore water profiles from the SG-1 station indicate that within the SMTZ, both sulfate driven AOM and OSR occurs. Each pathway accounted for about half of the total sulfate reduction, leading to maximum DIC concentration and

to minimum in $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ within the SMTZ. Despite sulfate concentrations in the SMTZ decreased below the detection limit, and previous shown ongoing sulfate reduction, no sulfide was detected in the SMTZ or in any other part of the sediment column. This indicates that the net sulfide consumption is equal to sulfate reduction. The consumption of sulfide can be related to the iron cycle. Sulfide can react with Fe(II) to form FeS (Eq. 10) or pyrite (FeS_2) (Rickard and Luther (2007); Eq. (11)).

Sulfide can also directly react with iron minerals, leading to iron reduction and elemental sulfur creation (Yao and Millero, 1993, 1996: Eq. 12).

This suggested reaction, combine with other iron and sulfide related reaction, can lead to "cryptic" sulfur cycle, as detailed in section 1.2. This connection between iron and sulfure cycles also implies a possible influence of iron minerals on the SMTZ, and sulfur involvement on the deep iron reduction.

From the Fe(II) profiles, there seems to be three phases of iron reduction (Fig. 6E), one phase is in the upper "classical" part of the sediment before sulfate is completely reduced, and the two others are in the methanogenesis depth, in 400 cm depth, and 600 cm depth. Usually, iron reduction is coupled to oxidation of organic matter (Lovley & Phillips, 1988) and is performed by iron reducing bacteria, which is probably the case in the upper part of the sediments. The question is, what mechanism and cycles are related to the deep iron reduction process, which occurs below the SMTZ. The geochemical profiles showed a maximum in methane concentrations (Fig. 6C) in 400 cm depth, parallel to a maximum in Fe(II) concentrations (Fig. 6E). According to this correlation, it is possible there is a connection between the iron and methane cycles, and involvement of methanogens in the deep anomaly iron reduction process (see section 1.5).

4.3.2 The connection between iron and sulfate-driven AOM in the SMTZ

Because of the possible connection between iron and sulfur cycles, implied from the profiles and previous publications, the first experiment in the Mediterranean continental shelf sediments was designed to explore the effect of the presence of iron oxides in the SMTZ on sulfate driven AOM. Specifically, Sivan et al. (2014) found that addition of hematite increased the sulfate-driven AOM in seeps, and I aimed to test the effect of such addition in diffused control profiles.

Experiment A results showed that MIR occurs in the SMTZ of the Mediterranean Continental Shelf. This is important, as the profiles could not provide this information, probably due to fast precipitation of any reduced iron with sulfide in this zone. Dissolved iron reached to a higher concentration in bottles containing hematite in the first week of the experiment (Fig. 8A), indicating a slightly faster iron reduction rate when hematite is supplied, but from the second week both natural and hematite added bottles showed same concentrations.

The question is what is the effect of this iron-oxide addition and its reduction on the other cycles? Although sulfate, DIC and methane concentration didn't show a clear change in concentration or significant difference between treatments, both $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ and $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ results indicate clearly that hematite addition inhibited sulfate driven AOM. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values became higher by 30-80‰ (Fig. 8D) in both natural bottles and bottles containing hematite, indicating significant oxidation of ^{13}C enriched methane, which was added to the bottles. Because $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ became higher in the natural bottles, it seems the methane oxidation in natural bottles is faster than in bottles containing hematite, meaning iron oxides presence inhibits sulfate driven AOM.

In addition, $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ in bottles containing both hematite and ^{13}C enriched bicarbonate (with no labeled ^{13}C methane) became lower by 300-360‰. In this case, the decrease in $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ can be explained by addition of light DIC, released from the oxidation of light (non-labeled) methane. These results also indicate that hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis (that uses the labeled ^{13}C - CO_2) is less significant from AOM in this zone, otherwise it would result in heavier DIC.

The results show nicely a significant changes in $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ (Fig. 8F), where it became heavier by 2.8‰ in natural bottles, and by 1.6-2.1‰ in bottles containing hematite (while, again, the sulfate concentrations were not sensitive enough to trace the activity).

As the concentration change was within the error, I could not calculate the exact fractionation in my experiment, however it seems small due to the long time of incubation and the only 1.6-2.8‰ change in $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ values. Low fractionation fits environment controlled by sulfate driven AOM (Deusner et al. 2014, Avrahamov et al. 2014, Sivan et al. 2014). Even with this low fractionation, the addition of molybdate also stopped the increase in the $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ value (Fig. 8D), which supports sulfate reduction by AOM. The abundances of bacteria, archaea, and *mcrA* gene (indicative for methanotrophs and methanogens) were significantly higher in samples from natural bottles comparing to samples from bottles containing hematite. This confirms that the hematite presence inhibits both methanotrophs and sulfate reducing bacteria. The abundances of bacteria and *mcrA* gene in samples from bottles containing hematite were very similar to T0 samples, but the number of copies of archaea gene in bottles containing hematite was twice as much as the number of copies of archaea gene in T0. This may indicate that different archaea, which doesn't have methane related metabolism are encouraged in the bottles containing hematite, maybe due to other processes as organoclastic iron reduction by methanogens (as was shown by Sivan et al., 2016).

4.3.3 Deep iron reduction and related cycles

In order to investigate which cycles and microbes are related to the deep iron reduction process, experiment B and C were designed. In those experiments, different iron oxides and different inhibitors were added to different bottles in an attempt to insulate a specific factor which inhibits or encourages the iron reduction process (see section 3.5.1). Unfortunately, most of the different treatments in experiment C didn't show a significant or consistent change in time, compared to the dead control identical treatment in the measured parameters (Fe(II), methane, DIC concentrations and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$). The only treatment that showed a clear trend was BES addition, in bottles with hematite or amorphous iron. BES is a methanogenesis/methanotrophy inhibitor, and was added in order to examine two possible connections between methanogenesis and iron reduction: 1) If there is a competition between iron reducing bacteria and methanogens, the BES will inhibit the hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis, and more hydrogen will be available for iron reduction. 2) If there is a syntrophy of methanotrophs and iron reducing bacteria or if the methanotrophs are reducing the iron oxides by oxidizing the

methane, then the addition of BES should inhibit also the iron reduction. In both experiments, B and C, Fe(II) concentrations increased consistently in non-killed bottles when BES was added to the sediment (Fig. 10C, Fig. 1S), which could imply that option 1, a competition between iron reducing bacteria and methanogens is the scenario in the sediment. It is also possible that the BES addition doesn't allow methanogenesis, and methanogens switch from methanogenesis to iron reduction as shown before (Sivan et al. 2016). Dead control bottles didn't show this increase, proving microbial iron reduction is the reason for this Fe(II) increase. However, two other observations contradict this explanation: 1) When Acetylene, which was also proven as an effective methanogenesis inhibitor (Sprott et al. 1982, Chan et al. 2000) was added to the same sediment with same iron oxides addition, Fe(II) concentrations didn't show the same significant and consistent increase. 2) $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ decreased in 8-10‰ in all nonkilled bottles containing BES, and DIC concentration increased in 3-4 mM (Fig. 10A,10B,3S; identical autoclaves bottles didn't show this changes in time). These observations lead to another explanation for the BES related iron reduction: BES act's as an electron donor for iron reduction. The isotopically light BES itself react with the iron oxides, transforms to light DIC, making the DIC lighter, and Fe(II) concentrations higher.

Another interesting result that can shed light on the connection between iron reduction and methanogenesis is $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ in experiment B. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ in natural bottles became higher in 5.2-7.5‰, while $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ in bottles containing amorphous iron kept a relatively stable value in 490 days, with a final value similar to the initial value and to the dead control bottle (Fig. 10A). The heavier DIC in the natural bottles can be explained by the oxidation of ^{13}C enriched methane, which was added to the bottles, to DIC during AOM, making it heavier. Previous researches already suggested deep AOM in diffusive marine profiles, but based mainly on models (Egger et al. 2017; Treude et al. 2014, Riedinger et al. 2014; Sivan, Schrag, and Murray 2007), in which the AOM was driven by iron reduction. If deep AOM was the reason for the enrichment in the $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$, we would expect it to be encouraged in bottles containing iron oxides and not delayed as the results show, and to reach a higher $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values after 490 days of experiment. Another explanation to the difference between the natural bottles to bottles containing amorphous iron is iron oxides inhibits methanogenesis, under iron-reducing conditions, due to competition between methanogens and iron-reducing bacteria for the common substrates acetate and hydrogen as shown before (Conrad 1999; Lovley and Phillips 1986; Roden 2003). In this case, the 5.2-7.5‰ increase in $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ in natural bottles is

due to methanogenesis, in which the residual DIC pool can become heavier by 50-70% (Whiticar, 1999; Borowski et al., 2000), that does not occur under iron reducing condition in the bottles containing amorphous iron.

5. Results and discussion - Yarqon Estuary

5.1 Porewater profiles

Geochemical profiles from the Yarqon estuary, sampled in June 18 (Fig. 12) and July 18 (Fig. 13), were made in order to understand the anaerobic respiration processes occurring in the Yarqon estuary sediments, and identify the sediment zone which is relevant for incubation experiments.

Sulfate concentrations decreased from 18.2 mM (Fig. 12A) and 25.7 mM (Fig. 13A) to below detection limit at 15 cm depth in both profiles. In June 18 sampling, Sulfide concentrations (Fig. 12B) were 31.8 μM in the water sediment interface, the decreased to 4 μM in 4 cm depth, increased again to 81.8 μM at 14 cm depth, decreased again to 56.8 μM in 16 cm depth, increased again to 130.4 μM at 20 cm depth, and decreased gradually to final concentration of 3.4 μM in 33 cm depth.

Fe(II) concentrations (Fig. 12B) was 10.5 in the water sediment interface, then decreased to 1.3 μM in 4 cm depth, and kept low concentration in range of 0.7 μM to 4 μM until the bottom of the core.

The methane concentrations (Fig. 12C) was 0.09 mM in pore water in 2 cm depth, increased to 0.3 mM in 4 cm depth, and kept on high concentrations in range of 0.4 mM to 1.4 mM until the bottom of the core, with two maximum concentration peaks of 1.39 mM and 0.96 mM at 6 and 18 cm depth.

Figure 12: Geochemical profiles from Yarqon estuary from June 18. A- Sulfate concentrations. B-Fe(II) and sulfide concentrations. C- Methane concentrations. D-DIC concentrations. E- $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values. F-Sediment porosity. Location of the sediments which were taken to incubation experiments D are marked in red.

DIC concentration (Fig. 12D) showed maximum of ~ 54.6 mM at 16 cm depth. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values (Fig. 12E) shows minimum of -20.7‰ at 2 cm depth, then increased gradually to -7.6‰ at 22 cm depth, and decreased again to -8.5‰ at 33 cm depth. Porosity (Fig. 12F) decreased from 81.2% in the top of the core to 59.7% at the bottom, with an average of 70.6%. According to these profiles, sediments from 6-22 cm depth were taken for incubation experiment D.

In July 18 sampling, Sulfide concentrations (Fig. 13B) were 148.1 μM in the water sediment interface, the decreased to 8.8 μM in 4 cm depth, increased again to 160.1 μM at 7 cm depth, decreased again to 2.4 μM in 14 cm depth, increased again to 14.9 μM at 16 cm depth, decreased to 3.6 μM in 18 cm depth, and kept on low concentrations in range of 0.7 μM to 5.4 μM until the bottom of the core.

The Fe(II) concentrations (Fig. 13B) showed maximum concentration of 12.4 μM at 3 cm depth, then decreased gradually to 2.7 μM in 8 cm depth, and kept low concentration in range of 2.2 μM to 3.8 μM until the bottom of the core.

Figure 13: Geochemical profiles from Yarqon estuary from July 18. A-Sulfate concentrations. B- Fe(II) and sulfide concentrations. C-Methane concentrations. D-DIC concentrations. E- $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values. Location of the sediments which were taken to incubation experiments E are marked in red.

The methane concentrations (Fig. 13C) was 0.2 mM in pore water in 3 cm depth, increased to 7.6 mM in 5 cm depth, decreased again to 1.08 mM in 7 cm depth, and kept on high concentrations in range of 0.54 mM to 6.6 mM until the bottom of the core, with maximum concentration picks of 6.6 mM at 15 cm depth.

DIC concentration (Fig. 13D) showed maximum of ~57.9 mM at 22 cm depth. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values (Fig.13E) showed minimum of -17.3‰ at 3 cm depth, then increased gradually to -6.8‰ at 26 cm depth, and kept this value until the bottom of the core. According to these profiles, sediments from 16-30 cm depth were taken for incubation experiment E.

5.2 Incubation experiments results

5.2.1 Incubation experiments D results

Experiment D (Fig. 14) was set up with 27 gram of sediment strait from the core (the sediment was mix for 10 minutes in N_2 flushed bag before divided into the experiments bottles, see section 3.5.2) and 55 grams of artificial sea water with 5 mM sulfate to final

water to sediment ratio of 2:1. In this experiment I quantified the iron reduction processes and their link to sulfate-coupled AOM in this zone. The incubations thus included additions of hematite, amorphous iron, molybdate, and labeled methane for one year. It is important to mention that in this experiment, duplicate bottles with the same

Figure 14: Experiment D anaerobic incubation bottles.

treatment didn't show same trends and results. Therefore, the sulfate, methane and DIC concentration and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ results (Fig. 15) are showed not according to identical treatment duplicates, but according to similar trends which seems to be controlled by sulfate consumption rates. Identical treatments have the same marker for comparison. Sulfate initial concentration was between 3.3 to 6.1 mM (Fig. 15A). Sulfate concentration in bottles containing molybdate and hematite decreased in ~3 mM in 361 days (from 4.5 mM and 5.3 mM to 1.5 mM and 3 mM, respectively). Sulfate concentration in the autoclaved bottle with amorphous iron decreased to 4.6 mM After 47 days, increased gradually to 5.1 mM after 266 days, and decreased again to a final concentration of 3.9 mM. Sulfate concentration in the autoclaved bottle with hematite was between 4.0 mM to 4.7 mM during the experiment. The other six bottles didn't have a similar decrease according to duplicate treatments, but can be divided into two groups: high sulfate consumption rate, and low sulfate consumption rate. Both groups showed higher sulfate consumption rate in compare to autoclaved and molybdate added bottles. In the high sulfate consumption rate group, sulfate concentration decreased to ~0.1 mM after 180 days and stayed under detection limit until the end of the experiment. In the low sulfate consumption rate group, sulfate concentration after 180 days was between 1.1 mM to 1.8 mM, decreased to ~0.7 mM after 266 days, and finally decrease to a value under detection limit in the end of the experiment after 361 days.

Figure 15: Experiment D results. Duplicate bottles with the same treatment didn't show same trends and results. Therefore, the results are showed not according to identical treatment duplicates, but according to similar trends which seems to be controlled by sulfate consumption rates. Turquoise lines represent three bottles with high sulfate consumption rate, and pink lines represent three bottles with lower sulfate consumption rate. Identical treatments have the same marker for comparison. A- SO_4 concentrations. B-Methane concentration in HS. C- $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values. D- DIC concentrations.

Methane was measured after 215 and 279 days. Methane initial amount in the experiment bottles was 0.11 mmol in head space according to dead control bottles. (Fig. 15B). After 211 days, the bottles with the higher sulfate consumption rate showed the highest methane amounts: 0.17 to 0.23 mmol in head space, then bottles containing

molybdate with 0.15 to 0.18 mmol in head space, and the bottles with the lower sulfate consumption rate showed the lowest methane amounts: 0.8 to 0.14, similar to the dead control bottles which showed only 0.11 mmol methane in head space. After 279 days, all nonkilled bottles showed a decrease in methane amounts in bottles. The bottles with the higher sulfate consumption rate still showed the highest amounts, this time of 0.13 to 0.16 mmol in head space, then bottles containing molybdate with 0.13 to 0.14 mmol in head space, and then the bottles with the lower sulfate consumption rate and dead control bottles, with 0.9 to 0.11 mmol methane in head space.

DIC concentrations increased in all bottles (Fig. 15D) during the 361 days of the experiment. DIC concentration in dead control bottles showed the smallest increase, from 10.5 mM and 10 mM to 12.3 mM and 13.4 mM, respectively. After the dead control bottles, bottles with molybdate and hematite showed the smallest increase, from 10.8 mM and 11.9 mM to 19.6 mM and 18.7 mM, respectively. DIC concentration showed the highest increase of ~12 mM in the bottles containing amorphous iron and bottles containing hematite with the higher sulfate consumption rate, rising from 12.5 mM to 24.7 mM, and from 12 mM to 24.4 mM, respectively. In the lower sulfate consumption rate bottles containing amorphous iron and hematite, DIC concentration increased only in ~9.8 mM, from ~12.2 mM to 22 mM. DIC concentration in natural bottles increased in ~8.7 mM, from 12.8 mM and 11.7 mM to 21.4 mM and 20.6 mM. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ initial value (Fig. 15C) in all bottles was ~-7‰. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ value in dead control bottles remained relatively stable with maximum of 2.6‰ change along the experiment. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ value in bottle containing both hematite and molybdate increased in 6.7‰ and 10.3‰, to final concentration of -0.2‰ and 3‰, respectively. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ value showed different trends with time in natural bottles, and in bottles containing amorphous iron or hematite. In the three bottles with the higher sulfate consumption rate, $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ value decreased in the first 104 days to -8.6‰, -11.4‰ and -13.9‰ in the natural bottle, bottle containing hematite, and bottle containing amorphous iron, respectively. After 104 days, sulfate concentration became depleted (Fig. 15A), and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ value in bottles with the higher sulfate consumption rate increased in 22‰ to 33‰, to final value of 24.7‰, 21.7‰ and 8‰, in the natural bottle, bottle containing hematite, and bottle containing amorphous iron, respectively. In the natural and hematite containing bottle with the lower sulfate consumption rate, $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ value increased in the first 104 days to -5.6‰ and -4.3‰, respectively, then decreased to -8‰ and -6.3‰ after 215 days, and increased again to final value of -2.2‰ and 0‰

after 361 days. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ value in the bottle containing amorphous iron with lower sulfate consumption rate decreased gradually to -10.9‰ after 215 days, and then increased to final value of -7.6‰ after 361 days.

Bottles containing amorphous iron showed the largest increase in Fe(II) concentrations (Fig.16). The bottle with the higher sulfate consumption rate between the duplicate bottles which contains amorphous iron reached to a maximum concentration of 434 μM after 180 days and decreased to 278 μM after 361 days, while its duplicate with lower sulfate consumption rate reached 278 μM final concentration after 361 days. The autoclaved bottle with amorphous iron reached only 186 μM maximum after 180 days and decreased to final concentration of 96 μM after 361 days. Fe(II) concentrations in bottles with molybdate and hematite increased to ~ 15 μM after 21 days, and decreased gradually to final concentration of ~ 1.5 μM after 361 days. Fe(II) initial concentrations in bottles with hematite was ~ 2 μM , and decreased to ~ 0.5 μM after 104. From this point, the duplicates showed different trends. In the bottle containing hematite with the lower sulfate consumption rate, the Fe(II) concentration kept the low value of ~ 0.5 μM until the end of the experiment. In the other duplicate containing hematite, when sulfate concentration decreased to 0.1 mM after 180 days, the Fe(II) concentration increased to 12 μM , and reached final concentration of 15 μM after 361 days. The Fe(II) concentration in autoclaved bottle with hematite increased gradually from 6.5 μM to ~ 37 μM during 361 days. Fe(II) initial concentrations in natural bottles was ~ 2.5 μM , decreased to ~ 0.3 μM after 47 days, and kept this low value until the end of the experiment.

Figure 16: Fe(II) concentrations in experiment D. The right graph is a close-up on 0-40 μM concentrations.

Natural bottles showed the largest increase in sulfide concentrations (Fig.17). The bottle with the higher sulfate consumption rate between the natural duplicates reached a maximum concentration of 598 μM after 104 days and decreased to 64 μM after 361 days, while its duplicate with lower sulfate consumption rate reached 418 μM final concentration after 361 days. Sulfide concentrations in bottles containing hematite increased to maximum of ~ 270 μM after 104 days, and from this point the duplicate showed different trends. In the bottle containing hematite with the lower sulfate consumption rate, the sulfide concentration stayed relatively high, and decreased to 52 μM in the end of the experiment after 361 days. In the other hematite added duplicate, when sulfate concentration decreased to 0.1 mM after 180 days, the sulfide concentration decreased to 15 μM , and reached final concentration of 16 μM after 361 days. Sulfide initial concentration in the autoclaved bottle with hematite was 150 μM , decreased rapidly to 66 μM after 6 days, and then decreased gradually to 7 μM after 266 days. Sulfide initial concentrations in bottles with molybdate and hematite was 54.9 μM and 38.9 μM , decreased to ~ 12 μM 47 days, and increased gradually to final concentration of ~ 60 μM after 361 days. Sulfide initial concentrations in bottles with amorphous iron was 60.7 μM and 31.7 μM , decreased rapidly to ~ 1 μM after 6 days, and reached a final concentration of ~ 1 μM after 361 days. Sulfide initial concentration

in the autoclaved bottle with amorphous iron was 137 μM , decreased rapidly to 4.8 μM after 6 days, and then decreased gradually to 2 μM after 361 days.

Figure 17: Sulfide concentrations in experiment D. The right graph is a close-up on 0-200 μM concentrations.

5.2.2 Incubation experiments E results

Experiment E was set up with 40 grams of 1:1 water to sediment ratio (sediment slurry from the 16-30 cm depth of July 18 sampling, see section 3.5.2) and 20 grams of artificial sea water with no sulfate to final water to sediment ratio of 3:1. Sulfate concentration was below detection limit (0.2 mM) in the experiment. In this experiment I investigate the mechanism and other related cycles and microbes of the iron reduction process in estuary sediments. The slurry was amended with hematite, magnetite, amorphous iron, BES, molybdate and labeled methane for 248 days. Fe(II) initial concentrations (Fig. 18) in all nonkilled bottles was $\sim 0.6 \mu\text{M}$, and in autoclaved bottles $\sim 4 \mu\text{M}$ (autoclaved bottles were sampled after the autoclave). Bottles containing amorphous iron showed the largest increase in Fe(II) concentration, to a final concentration of $\sim 44 \mu\text{M}$ after 248 days. Fe(II) concentration in bottles containing magnetite and BES reached $\sim 24 \mu\text{M}$ after 248 days. Fe(II) concentration increased in all other nonkilled bottles, to final concentration in range of $2.8 \mu\text{M}$ to $6.6 \mu\text{M}$, bottles containing magnetite showed the largest increase and natural bottles showed the smallest increase. Fe(II) concentration in autoclaved bottles containing amorphous iron increased to $48 \mu\text{M}$ after 5 days, and then decreased gradually to final concentration of $40 \mu\text{M}$ after 248 days. Fe(II) concentration in autoclaved bottles containing magnetite

increased gradually to final concentration of 5.5 μM , and Fe(II) concentration autoclaved bottles containing magnetite and BES increased gradually to final concentration of 11 μM after 248 days.

Figure 18: Fe(II) concentrations in experiment E. The left graph is a close-up on 0-12 μM concentrations.

Sulfide initial concentrations in nonkilled bottles (Fig.19) was between 7.5 μM to 27.8 μM , natural bottles showed the highest initial concentration and bottles containing amorphous iron showed the lowest concentration. Sulfide concentrations in natural bottles increased in the first 13 days to ~ 45 μM , and then decrease gradually to final concentration of ~ 20 μM after 248 days. Sulfide concentrations in bottles containing hematite increased in the first 5 days to ~ 27 μM , and then decrease gradually to final concentration of ~ 20 μM after 248 days. Sulfide concentrations in bottles containing magnetite and magnetite with molybdate stayed relatively stable with 4 μM variation, and in bottles containing magnetite with BES or amorphous iron sulfide concentration decrease under detection limit after 13 days. Sulfide initial concentrations in autoclaved bottles was ~ 85 μM (autoclaved bottles were sampled after the autoclave), and decrease rapidly to under detection limit after 13 and 26 days in dead bottles containing amorphous iron and dead bottles containing both magnetite and BES, respectively. Sulfide concentrations in autoclaved bottles containing only magnetite decreased gradually to final concentration of 20 μM after 248 days.

Figure 19: Sulfide concentrations in experiment E. The left graph is a close-up on 0-60 μM concentrations.

DIC initial concentration in all nonkilled bottles was 10 mM, and ~ 8 mM in autoclaved bottles (Fig. 20A). Concentration in all nonkilled bottles increased in 0.7 mM to 2.2 mM in the 248 days of the experiment, bottles containing hematite, magnetite, and BES showed the largest increase and bottles containing amorphous iron showed the smallest increase. Concentration in autoclaved bottles containing magnetite kept a relatively stable value with 0.8 variation, and concentration in the autoclaved bottle containing amorphous iron increase to final concentration of 10.1 mM.

The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ initial value in all non-killed bottles was $\sim 14.6\text{‰}$, and $\sim 13\text{‰}$ in autoclaved bottles (Fig. 20B). The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ in all bottles except natural bottles, bottles containing hematite and bottles containing both magnetite and BES, increase in 0.2 ‰ to 2.5 ‰ , including dead control bottles. Natural bottles showed the highest increase of $\sim 15.4\text{‰}$ in $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$, reaching to values between -0.3 ‰ to 1.6 ‰ after 248 days. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ value in bottles containing hematite increase in 11.9 ‰ and 9.8 ‰ after 248 days, with final value of -2.8 ‰ and -4.7 ‰ , respectively. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ value in bottles containing both magnetite and BES decrease in 1.7 ‰ and 5.4 ‰ after 248 days, with final value of -16.3 ‰ and -19.9 ‰ , respectively.

Figure 20: DIC concentrations and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ in experiment E. A- DIC concentrations

B- $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$

5.3 Discussion

5.3.1 The depth of the microbial processes in the Yarqon estuary

The two cores, which were sampled in June and July 2018, show different sulfate concentration in the sediment-water interface (18.2 mM Fig.12A and 25.7 mM Fig.13A). Because the cores were sampled 3 km upstream, where seawater penetrates the sediment pores, the salinity can change rapidly between different sampling times and small location differences, according to the Yarqon river level and flow. Fe(II) profiles (Fig.12B,13B) shows only the classic iron reduction coupled to the oxidation of organic matter in the upper part of the sediment, and the Fe(II) concentration reach a maximum of only 12.5 μM close to sediment-water interface, but no deep iron reduction areas as seen in the Mediterranean Sea and many other marine and freshwater profiles (Sivan et al., 2011; Riedinger et al. 2014; Treude et al. 2014; Egger et al. 2017). This could be explained by two options: 1) In the sampled sediments, there is no iron reduction beneath 5 cm depth. 2) Similar to the absences of sulfide in the Mediterranean Sea, iron can react with sulfide which is in high concentrations in the deeper part of the sediment (Fig.12B,13B), to form FeS (Eq. 10) or pyrite (FeS_2) Eq. (11), creating net Fe(II) consumption equal to iron reduction. It was already shown in previous studies that organo-clastic sulfate reduction, sulfate-driven AOM, and methanogenesis co-exist in the Yarqon estuary (Antler et al. 2014, Sela-Adler et al., 2017), leading to the

question: does iron reduction also occurs beneath 5 cm depth, and what is the relationship between the iron reduction and the other metabolic pathways in the Yarqon estuary sediments?

5.3.2 Iron reduction potential

In order to examine the iron reduction potential and how iron oxides presence effects the Yarqon estuary sediments, two experiments were designed: experiment D with shallow sediments, were according to the geochemical profiles sulfate is being consume, methane is already produced, and sulfide concentrations are high, and experiment E with sediments from the deeper part, were sulfate and sulfide concentration are depleted.

In both experiments, when amorphous iron (which is relatively available for reduction) was supplied, Fe(II) concentrations increased up to 434 μM in the shallow sediments (Fig.16) and 44.5 μM in the deeper sediments (Fig.18), proving iron reduction potential below 5 cm in the Yarqon sediments. In experiment D, when hematite or magnetite (which are less available for reduction compered to amorphous iron) were added to the sediments, Fe(II) concentrations increased only when sulfate reduction inhibitor was added or sulfate concentration reached below 0.3 mM, probably because of thermodynamical consideration (redox). In experiment E, Fe(II) concentrations increased in all bottles. The next significant increase after the amorphous iron containing bottles was in bottles containing both magnetite and BES, probably because BES act's as an electron donor for iron reduction according to the decrease in $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ (see section 4.3.3). In the rest of the bottles, the increase was in 2.2-5.7 μM . The largest increase was in bottles containing both magnetite and molybdate (sulfate reduction and sulfur disproportion inhibitor), and the smallest increase (but still exist) was in the natural bottles. This proves that iron reduction can occur in the natural deep sulfate depleted sediments, and is encouraged when even less available iron oxides are supply or when sulfate reduction is inhibited.

5.3.3 Sulfate reduction, methanogenesis and AOM

Sela-Adler et al. (2017) showed that sulfate reduction and methanogenesis co-exist in the Yarqon estuary, where the main factors controlling methanogenesis initiation and intensity are sulfate reduction **rate** and **substrate** availability. Experiment D results

support this conclusion. Sulfate concentrations and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values (Fig 15A, 15C) show that in bottles with **high sulfate consumption rate** (see section 5.2.1), $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values decrease as long as sulfate concentrations are above 0.3 mM, probably due to organo-clastic sulfate reduction. After 104 days, when sulfate reaches below detection limit, $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values start to increase, due to methanogenesis or AOM processes. Another interesting observation is that $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values increase in $\sim 2.7\%$ in the first 47 days, before starting to decrease until 266 days, in the natural bottles and bottles containing hematite with **low sulfate consumption rate**. This could be explained also by sulfate reduction rate controlling methanogenesis intensity. Because of the initial low sulfate consumption rate, methanogenesis initiated early in those bottles, leaving its signature on $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values. In a later stage, after 104 days, when organo-clastic sulfate reduction products are more significant than methanogenesis products, $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ value decrease due to light organic matter oxidation. Finally, $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values started to increase after 266 days, when sulfate concentration decreased below 1 mM, and methanogenesis or AOM become more dominant. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values in bottles containing both hematite and molybdate also support this theory. These bottles show similar values in the first 47 days to bottles with lower sulfate consumption rate, and then continued to increase along all of the experiment, with final increase of 4.8-7.2‰, which also can be explained by methanogenesis. Methane amounts (Fig 15B) after 211 days were also higher in bottles with high sulfate consumption rate and in bottles containing both hematite and molybdate, proving that in this stage methanogenesis was more significant in these bottles when sulfate was depleted or sulfate reduction was inhibited.

In experiment D, after sulfate was depleted and until the end of the experiment, $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ in bottles with **high sulfate consumption rates** became heavier by 21.8-33.5‰. In experiment E, $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ in natural bottle became heavier by 14.4-16.1‰ and in bottles containing hematite has gotten heavier by 9.8-11.9‰. This increase in $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ was higher than the natural isotope fractionation increase in methanogenesis (as shown in bottles containing molybdate), and probably caused by significant oxidation of ^{13}C enriched methane which was added to the bottles, proving that AOM occurs in both shallow and deep sediment (in different rates) when sulfate concentrations were low. In both experiments, bottles containing molybdate didn't show any increase, proving the AOM is driven by sulfate reduction even when it is in very low concentrations.

In Experiment E, because the DIC became heavier in the natural bottles compared to bottles containing hematite, it seems the AOM in natural bottles is faster than in

bottles containing hematite. This means that iron oxides presence inhibits sulfate driven AOM, similarly to the observations in experiment A from the Mediterranean continental shelf. The question is why should iron oxides inhibit the reaction between sulfate and methane? It seems that there may be 4 possible scenarios: 1) Iron oxides addition changes the natural redox conditions in the sediments, which causes a change in the potential intermediates in the environment. 2) Iron reduction uses species that are needed for sulfate AOM and thus competes with this process on these species. 3) The microbes, which are involved in the sulfate driven AOM process (sulfate reducers or methanotrophs), switch to iron reduction when iron oxides are added, similarly to methanogens switch from methanogenesis to iron reduction as proven before (Sivan et al. 2016). 4) Iron oxides addition stimulate iron reduction, which result in Fe(II) production. The Fe(II) can react with the sulfides to form FeS (Eq. 10) or pyrite (FeS₂) Eq. (11), so the sulfides can no longer react to form sulfate again. Further study is needed in order to identify the coupling between sulfur methane and iron in these systems.

6. Summary and conclusions

The purpose of this study was to shed light on iron reduction processes that are far deeper than the expected iron oxide redox zone. Although peaks in Fe(II) were observed in the methanic zone of many marine sediments, the type of iron reduction (biotic/abiotic), its mechanisms and the related processes have still not been shown in geochemical lab experiments on natural sediments. For this purpose, two marine environments were chosen, which have similar salinity, but different in their organic matter content, and were studied for other processes before: The oligotrophic continental shelf of the SE Mediterranean, and the organic rich Yarqon Estuary.

In the continental shelf of the SE Mediterranean, deep iron reduction was observed in both geochemical profiles and lab experiments. The experiments showed that iron reduction occurs in the SMTZ, although it is not the main process occurring in this depth, and also in the deep methanogenesis zone. In addition, the experiments showed iron oxides presence inhibits both sulfate driven AOM and methanogenesis. It is not clear if the inhibition is due to a competition between iron reducing bacteria and other microorganisms for substrates even in zones iron reduction is not the dominant process,

or due to a change in natural redox conditions in the sediments when iron oxides are added.

In the rich organic matter Yarqon estuary, iron reduction was observed only in the classic upper zone in the geochemical profiles, but lab experiments in shallow and deep sediments showed the potential for deep iron reduction, which is inhibited by sulfate reduction, and encouraged by iron oxides supply or sulfate inhibitors.

AOM process was observed in sediments from SE Mediterranean SMTZ, and in both shallow and deep sediments of the Yarqon estuary. Although models suggested deep iron driven AOM in diffusive marine profiles, the observed AOM in this study was due to sulfate reduction, even in low sulfate concentrations, and iron oxides inhibit AOM in both environments. The experiments with sediments from the Yarqon estuary showed sulfate reduction rate is the main factor controlling all other processes (iron reduction, methanogenesis and AOM), and only when sulfate concentration became depleted, or sulfate reduction rate decreased, the other processes were observed.

The main difference between the two environments, affected from organic matter content in the sediments, was the vertical distance between the different redox zones. In the SE Mediterranean Sea, the low organic carbon content causes a wide spread of the various redox zones (even though relatively to other marine shelf it is shorter). According to the geochemical profiles there is a ~2 meter distance between the SMTZ, where sulfate is available and sulfate reduction is the dominant process, and the methanogenic deep zone with anomaly Fe(II) peaks which was studied. Due to less diffusion between the zones and larger separation between the active microbes there is a significant separation between the processes occurring in the SMTZ and the deep methanogenesis zone.

In the Yarqon estuary, with significantly higher organic carbon content, all redox cascade processes occur within 30 centimeters and there is only a few centimeters that separate between the different zones. Therefore, the diffusion distance and time is much shorter, so that sulfate and sulfide can penetrate the deeper sediments even in very low (under detection limit) concentrations. This can explain the results in the Yarqon estuary, which showed sulfate AOM in the SMTZ and in the deep methanogenesis zone, while in the SE Mediterranean sediments, sulfate AOM was the dominant process only in the SMTZ.

7. Supplmentry data

7.1 Eexperiment A data tables.

Table 1S: Experiment A FE(II) concentrations

		uM	uM	uM	uM	uM	5 mM hematite		uM	uM	uM	Artificial SW+5 mM hematite			
							addition								
days	0	4	18	42	63	134	154	163	224	310	438	475	487	501	563
treatment															
Hematite1	24.8	54.8	57.9	56.0	51.7	50.5	50.8	46.2	47.4	47.9	53.5	30.7	39.9	38.4	37.0
Hematite2	24.8	54.6	54.7	54.3	47.7	50.2	50.0	46.2	46.9	48.1	53.9	32.8	43.0	42.6	42.8
Natural1	24.8	43.5	51.4	52.7	48.9	48.4	50.4	44.7	45.2	45.5	51.3	29.5	36.6	36.7	38.4
Natural2	24.8	39.1	56.1	52.2	49.1	50.7	54.2	47.1	48.0	47.2	54.3	27.1	36.5	36.4	37.5
Dead1	26.2	26.2	27.6	26.9	20.7	24.6	24.5	17.2	20.4	17.8	22.6	10.9	15.5	15.9	13.7
Dead2	23.4	23.4	26.5	26.3	22.3	23.7	23.8	19.2	20.8	20.1	21.9	11.1	15.5	15.6	15.3

Table 2S: Experiment A CH₄ concentrations

	mmol in HS				
days	0	69	142	226	324
treatment					
Hematite1	0.05	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.06
Hematite2	0.06	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.04
Natural1	0.07	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.05
Natural2	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.06	0.06
Dead1	0.07	0.07	0.06	0.07	0.07
Dead2	0.07	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.07

Table 3S: Experiment A DIC concentrations

	mM	Artificial SW+5 mM hematite								
								+1 mM molybdate		
days	0	63	134	163	224	310	438	475	501	563
treatment										
Hematite1	7.5	5.0	6.9	5.7	5.9	5.4	6.0	3.8	3.9	3.91
Hematite2	7.6		6.5	5.6	5.8	5.3	5.7	4.0	3.8	4.08
Natural1	7.8	5.1	6.7	5.6	6.0	5.7	6.2	3.8	4.1	3.69
Natural2	7.5	5.0	6.7	5.6	6.0	5.6	6.1	4.1	4.2	3.92
Dead1	6.9	6.0	8.1	6.6	6.6	5.9	6.0	3.5	3.6	3.33
Dead2	7.4	5.2	8.1	6.7	6.7	5.7	6.2	3.4	3.5	3.45

Table 4S: Experiment A $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values

	‰	‰	‰	5 mM hematite			‰	‰	‰	Artificial SW+5 mM hematite		
				addition						+1 mM molybdate		
days	0	63	134	154	163	224	310	438	475	501	563	
treatment												
Hematite1	-16.0	-2.9	10.7	10.4	14.6	22.4	30.8	44.3	37.5	33.9	34.8	
Hematite2	-15.9	-3.3	5.4	3.8	7.8	11.5	15.3	18.5	15.2	15.3	14.8	
Natural1	-15.6	-6.3	8.6	9.4	13.8	25.0	39.2	65.1	55.2	59.8	51.9	
Natural2	-17.0	-6.1	8.2	8.1	12.9	22.1	33.3	50.6	44.1	41.9	41.8	
Labeled bicarbonate1	1653.6	1550.1	1457.3	1459.0	1413.0	1419.4	1313.7	1290.8				
Labeled bicarbonate2	1466.8	1385.3	1276.7	1289.4	1262.8	1264.5	1169.1	1159.0				
Dead1	-4.9		-5.5	-8.6	-6.3	-5.5	-4.2		-5.4	-3.2	-5.9	
Dead2	-6.4	-7.0	-6.2	-10.5	-7.5	-7.4	-6.1		-7.0	-6.1	-7.0	

Table 5S: Experiment A SO_4 concentrations

	mM	mM	mM	mM	mM	mM	Artificial SW+5 mM hematite	
							+1 mM molybdate	
days	4	63	134	224	310	454	471	497
treatment								
Hematite1	8.3	8.1	8.0	7.8	7.8	6.5	7.0	7.1
Hematite2	8.2	8.2	8.6	7.9	8.0	7.6	7.4	6.8
Natural1	8.1	8.1	7.8	8.1	7.8	8.4	6.7	7.2
Natural2	8.2	8.2	8.0	8.4	7.9	8.6	7.0	7.0
Dead1	8.3	8.5	8.5	8.0	8.0	7.4	6.7	7.2
Dead2	8.5	8.4	8.3	8.3	8.7	8.6	7.4	6.9

Table 6S: Experiment A $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ values

	‰	‰	‰	‰	‰	‰
days	4	63	134	224	310	438
treatment						
Hematite1	5.4	5.6	6	6.2	6.8	7.5
Hematite2	5.4	5.8	6	6.1		7
Natural1	5.3	5.7	6.1	6.5	7.1	8.1
Natural2	5.3	5.7	5.9	6.4	7.1	8.1
Dead1	5.6	5.6	5.7	5.5	5.7	5.7
Dead2	5.6	5.8	5.5	5.6	5.6	5.6

Table 7S: Experiment A abundance of bacteria, archaea, and mcrA genes

	bacteria	archaea	mcrA
Hematite1	9.52E+06	2.16E+07	3.68E+05
Hematite2	1.33E+07	2.61E+07	7.47E+05
Natural1	3.16E+07	5.47E+07	1.96E+06
Natural2	2.57E+07	4.91E+07	1.59E+06
T0	8.42E+06	1.09E+07	3.30E+05

7.2 Experiment B data tables

Table 8S: Experiment B Fe(II) concentrations

	μM										
days	0	1	2	9	18	30	79	165	281	388	490
treatment											
natural	108.5	83.9	120.1	141.4	120.6	119.6	126.2	126.9	149.3	152.8	154.8
natural	111.9	116.8	119.8	140.9	117.2	123.4	124.5	126.7	151.9	151.9	142.6
Amorphous iron	91.2	104.1	118.6	130.4	110.8	110.2	106.3	107.0	129.4	120.6	117.1
Amorphous iron	84.7	104.7	110.9	130.9	110.5	111.5	100.6	105.4	130.9	121.9	127.8
Amorphous iron+BES	95.4	113.4	118.6	165.9	124.3	131.6	123.6	131.5	203.5	206.8	256.8
Amorphous iron+BES	80.4	109.8	121.1	157.6	110.0	114.2	119.7	139.8	200.3	221.5	239.3
Dead+A. iron+BES		95.5	118.5	169.4	118.2	97.2	132.8	128.7	161.9	160.3	158.1
Dead+A. iron+BES		94.9	117.9	183.6	140.8	92.2	132.3	131.4	153.7	159.5	152.7

Table 9S: Experiment B DIC concentrations

	mM	mM	mM	mM	mM	mM	mM	mM	mM	mM
days	0	2	18	30	79	165	281	388	490	
treatment										
natural	6.2	5.5	4.8	5.5	5.3	4.9	5.2	5.7	5.7	
natural	6.3		4.6	5.3	4.9	4.9	5.2	5.6	5.8	
Amorphous iron	5.1	5.3	4.4	5.1	4.9	4.9	5.4	5.6	6.1	
Amorphous iron	5.6	5.1	4.4	5.1	4.8	4.8	5.4	5.6	5.9	
Amorphous iron+BES	3.8	4.9	4.5	5.2	5.3	5.3	6.4	6.6	7.1	
Amorphous iron+BES	5.8	5.1	4.5	5.1	5.2	5.3	6.3	6.6	7.4	
Dead+A. iron+BES	10.4	8.6	8.4	9.6	8.5	7.6	8.3	8.3	8.4	
Dead+A. iron+BES	9.7	8.7	8.1	9.4	8.2	7.7	8.2	8.3	8.6	

Table 10S: Experiment B $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values

	‰	‰	‰	‰	‰	‰	‰	‰	‰	‰
days	0	2	18	30	79	165	281	388	490	
treatment										
natural	-9.8	-9.9	-8.0	-9.4	-9.1		-10.6	-4.6	-2.3	
natural	-11.0	-11.8	-10.2	-11.4	-11.4	-11.1	-5.3	-5.9	-11.5	
Amorphous iron	-10.5	-10.7	-9.2	-10.5	-10.3	-10.1	-9.9	-10.8	-9.8	
Amorphous iron	-8.0	-8.3	-7.2	-8.2	-8.2	-8.2	-8.2	-9.2	-9.1	
Amorphous iron+BES	-7.8	-9.8	-9.3	-10.5	-11.6	-9.0	-13.1	-17.4	-18.0	
Amorphous iron+BES	-8.1	-9.8	-9.6	-11.0	-11.9	-14.2	-16.6	-17.9	-17.6	
Dead+A. iron+BES	-7.8	-9.1	-8.1	-9.0	-8.9	-8.8	-8.7	-9.3	-8.5	
Dead+A. iron+BES	-8.1	-8.9	-8.0	-9.1	-9.1	-8.9	-8.8	-9.2	-8.5	

7.3 Experiment C results and data tables

The experiment was set up from four different 1:1 slurry incubation (Table 11S), without mixing them before dividing into different treatments. As a result, bottles that were set up from different slurry incubations had different initial values in Fe(II) and DIC parameters.

Table 11S: Experiment C-bottles distribution from different slurry incubation bottles

		treatment
Slurry incubation bottle 1	C1+C2	
	C3+C4	Hematite
	C5+C6	Hematite+BES
	C7+C8	Hematite+molybdate
	C9	Hematite+magnetite
Slurry incubation bottle 2	C10	Hematite+magnetite
	C11+C12	Hematite+ acetylene
	C13+C14+C19+C20	Amorphous iron
	C15+C16	Amorphous iron+BES
	C17+C18	Amorphous iron+molybdate
Slurry incubation bottle 3	C21+C22	Amorphous iron+acetylene
	C23+C24	Amorphous iron+AQDS
	C37	Hematite
	C38	
Slurry incubation bottle 4	C25+C26 (killed)	Amorphous iron+acetylene
	C27+C28 (killed)	Hematite+BES
	C29+C30 (killed)	Hematite+ acetylene
	C31+C32 (killed)	Amorphous iron+hematite+molybdate
	C33+C34 (killed)	Amorphous iron
	C35+C36 (killed)	Amorphous iron+ AQDS

Table 12S: Experiment C Fe(II) concentrations

		0	7	21	60	132	248	363
treatment	Bottle number	μM						
Natural	C1	107.4	106.2	104.5	105.5	104.9	120.6	117.7
Natural	C2	100.4	100.3	101.5	105.3	96.9	101.6	98.1
Hematite	C3	97.8	98.4	113.9	95.3	95.3	96.5	95.0
Hematite	C4	99.6	99.4	100.6	102.0	101.8	98.3	100.1
BES+Hematite	C5	101.0	99.8	99.5	103.1	105.5	120.8	129.9
BES+Hematite	C6	98.5	99.0	113.4	100.9	108.2	124.2	129.7
Molybdate+Hematite	C7	98.2	98.0	115.0	102.5	100.2	97.0	95.0
Molybdate+Hematite	C8	95.2	111.4	121.7	101.9	100.5	95.7	92.6
Magnetite	C9	89.2	92.9	104.4	87.8	78.7	76.2	73.5
Magnetite	C10	127.1	127.6	128.3	122.5	118.3	118.7	113.7
Acetylene+Hematite	C11	128.5	127.0	128.4	132.6	131.9	128.7	130.5
Acetylene+Hematite	C12	129.1	131.5	128.9	129.6	125.7	127.1	125.6
Amorphous iron	C13	139.9	145.7	132.3	116.8	124.2	152.1	121.2
Amorphous iron	C14	141.6	111.6	143.7	125.2	124.4	124.3	123.3
BES+A. iron	C15	143.6	147.2	146.2	138.9	163.7	203.6	208.7
BES+A. iron	C16	138.1		137.4	139.4	168.4	186.7	218.0
Molybdate+A. iron	C17	129.4	125.5	116.2	110.8	111.4	105.3	106.1
Molybdate+A. iron	C18	125.7	131.3	117.3	116.7	116.2	109.1	104.4
Amorphous iron	C19	131.1	128.7	118.2	119.0	119.4	121.3	121.6

Amorphous iron	C20	135.3	133.7	128.0	109.8	120.2	117.2	117.8
Acetylene+A. iron	C21	102.3	133.3	126.0	120.9	118.0	114.0	112.3
Acetylene+A. iron	C22	130.9	136.6	125.7	119.7	114.0	112.6	112.7
AQDS+A. iron	C23	110.7	81.1	82.1	95.8	99.4	98.3	101.8
AQDS+A. iron	C24	113.1	82.1	66.2	92.4	80.3	100.1	95.2
Dead BES+Hematite	C27	69.2	53.0	52.7	55.9	59.1	63.5	61.2
Dead BES+Hematite	C28	76.9	55.6	59.8	59.8	63.3	66.1	64.8
Dead Acetylene+Hematite	C29	77.8	51.1	51.3	53.4	52.2	49.7	46.9
Dead Acetylene+Hematite	C30	77.4	52.6	53.1	54.7	53.5	46.3	45.3
Dead Molybdate+A. iron+Hematite	C31	78.1	88.4	92.9	86.0	75.6	68.3	64.3
Dead Molybdate+A. iron+Hematite	C32	77.6	95.0	93.6	80.1	72.4	70.4	61.2
Dead Amorphous iron	C33	77.6	164.2	174.1	141.9	123.0	142.1	100.3
Dead Amorphous iron	C34	76.9	164.6	156.4	132.1	118.8	88.6	100.1
Dead AQDS+A. iron	C35	82.4	105.8	95.2	95.9	64.0	82.8	71.6
Dead AQDS+A. iron	C36	76.6	107.5	99.7	97.0	71.3	71.8	72.4
Dead Acetylene+A. iron	C25	81.7	153.0	148.0	140.2	116.7	99.2	98.5
Dead Acetylene+A. iron	C26	76.3	151.7	147.4	140.5	115.2	130.2	104.7
Hematite	C37	103.5	110.3	110.8	109.9	114.8	128.2	105.0
Natural	C38	109.6	117.7	112.9	117.1	114.6	114.5	109.8

Table 13S: Experiment C DICconcentrations

		0	60	132	248	363
treatment	Bottle number	mM	mM	mM	mM	mM
Natural	C1	3.3	3.8	3.7	3.6	4.0
Natural	C2	3.2	3.9	3.7	3.8	4.1
Hematite	C3	3.2	4.0	3.7	3.8	4.2
Hematite	C4	3.3	3.9	3.8	3.8	4.1
BES+Hematite	C5	3.2	4.0	4.2	4.7	5.3
BES+Hematite	C6	3.1	4.1	4.1	4.7	5.1
Molybdate+Hematite	C7	3.1	3.9	3.5	3.7	4.0
Molybdate+Hematite	C8	3.1	3.8	3.5	3.7	3.9
Magnetite	C9	3.3	3.9	3.6	3.8	4.0
Magnetite	C10	4.4	5.4	5.3	5.1	5.2
Acetylene+Hematite	C11	4.7	5.7	6.3	5.6	5.9
Acetylene+Hematite	C12	4.6	5.9	5.9	5.5	5.8
Amorphous iron	C13	4.2	5.4	5.8	5.3	5.6
Amorphous iron	C14	4.1	5.4	5.8	5.4	5.6
BES+A. iron	C15	4.0	5.5	6.2	6.2	6.8
BES+A. iron	C16	4.0	5.7	6.0	6.3	6.8
Molybdate+A. iron	C17	4.1	5.4	5.2	5.3	5.6
Molybdate+A. iron	C18	4.1	5.3	5.3	5.3	5.6

Amorphous iron	C19	4.2	5.5	5.4	5.5	5.8
Amorphous iron	C20	4.0	4.6	5.2	5.4	5.8
Acetylene+A. iron	C21	3.7	4.3	5.1	4.9	5.5
Acetylene+A. iron	C22	3.6	4.7	4.6	4.9	5.0
AQDS+A. iron	C25	3.7	4.9	4.4	4.9	5.1
AQDS+A. iron	C26	3.7	4.9	4.6	4.6	5.1
Dead BES+Hematite	C27	6.1	6.2	5.6	5.4	5.8
Dead BES+Hematite	C28	6.1	6.1	5.4	5.3	5.8
Dead Acetylene+Hematite	C29	6.2	6.1	5.6	5.6	6.0
Dead Acetylene+Hematite	C30	6.4	6.2	5.7	5.6	6.0
Dead Molybdate+A. iron+Hematite	C31	6.2	5.8	5.0	4.1	5.3
Dead Molybdate+A. iron+Hematite	C32	6.2	5.6	6.1	5.0	5.3
Dead Amorphous iron	C33	6.2	7.7	7.1	7.0	7.3
Dead Amorphous iron	C34	6.3	7.7	6.4	7.2	7.4
Dead AQDS+A. iron	C35	6.4	6.2	5.8	5.5	6.0
Dead AQDS+A. iron	C36	6.4	6.3	7.7	5.7	5.3
Dead Acetylene+A. iron	C25	6.3	8.0	7.2	6.9	7.7
Dead Acetylene+A. iron	C26	6.3	8.0	6.0	7.1	7.6
Hematite	C37	4.1	4.9	4.9	4.3	5.2
Natural	C38	4.1	4.8	4.8	4.6	5.2

Table 14S: Experiment C $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ concentrations

		0	60	132	248	363
treatment	Bottle number	‰	‰	‰	‰	‰
Natural	C1	-10.4	-9.2	-9.4	-9.7	-10.4
Natural	C2	-10.4	-9.7	-9.6	-10.1	-10.7
Hematite	C3	-10.4	-9.4	-9.7	-10.2	-10.7
Hematite	C4	-10.3	-9.6	-9.7	-10.1	-10.8
BES+Hematite	C5	-10.2	-12.2	-15.9	-18.8	-19.7
BES+Hematite	C6	-10.2	-12.0	-15.8	-18.7	-19.5
Molybdate+Hematite	C7	-10.0	-9.2	-9.7	-9.9	-10.3
Molybdate+Hematite	C8	-10.1	-9.4	-9.6	-10.0	-10.3
Magnetite	C9	-10.3	-9.3	-9.5	-10.0	-10.4
Magnetite	C10	-11.8	-11.4	-11.6	-11.6	-11.9
Acetylene+Hematite	C11	-12.0	-11.5	-11.6	-11.6	-12.1
Acetylene+Hematite	C12	-11.6	-11.2	-11.5	-11.2	-11.8
Amorphous iron	C13	-11.5	-11.6	-11.6	-11.6	-11.9
Amorphous iron	C14	-11.4	-11.6	-11.5	-11.5	-12.0
BES+A. iron	C15	-11.4	-13.4	-15.9	-18.8	-19.9
BES+A. iron	C16	-12.2	-13.8	-16.5	-18.9	-20.1
Molybdate+A. iron	C17	-12.2	-12.3	-12.1	-12.4	-12.7
Molybdate+A. iron	C18	-12.2	-12.1	-12.2	-12.2	-12.4
Amorphous iron	C19	-12.2	-11.8	-12.2	-12.3	-12.6
Amorphous iron	C20	-12.0	-11.8	-12.3	-12.1	-12.5
Acetylene+A. iron	C21	-11.5	-11.0	-11.0	-11.2	-11.7

Acetylene+A. iron	C22	-11.3	-11.5	-11.5	-11.7	-12.1
AQDS+A. iron	C25	-11.8	-11.6	-11.8	-12.0	-12.2
AQDS+A. iron	C26	-11.8	-11.5	-11.6	-11.7	-12.2
Dead BES+Hematite	C27	-5.6	-4.7	-4.9	-4.6	-5.0
Dead BES+Hematite	C28	-7.1	-6.2	-6.1	-5.9	-6.4
Dead Acetylene+Hematite	C29	-7.3	-5.9	-6.2	-6.3	-6.7
Dead Acetylene+Hematite	C30	-7.4	-6.5	-6.3	-6.2	-6.6
Dead Molybdate+A. iron+Hematite	C31	-7.5	-6.8	-6.9	-6.1	-7.0
Dead Molybdate+A. iron+Hematite	C32	-7.2	-6.8	-7.5	-6.6	-6.8
Dead Amorphous iron	C33	-7.5	-8.6	-8.3	-8.0	-8.5
Dead Amorphous iron	C34	-7.4	-8.5	-7.9	-8.1	-8.4
Dead AQDS+A. iron	C35	-7.4	-7.2	-7.4	-7.1	-7.6
Dead AQDS+A. iron	C36	-7.4	-7.4	-7.9	-7.2	-7.6
Dead Acetylene+A. iron	C25	-7.4	-8.4	-8.4	-8.4	-8.6
Dead Acetylene+A. iron	C26	-7.6	-8.4	-9.4	-8.3	-8.6
Hematite	C37	-10.3	-10.5	-10.5	-9.7	-11.2
Natural	C38	-10.4	-10.4	-10.9	-10.5	-11.2

Table 15S: Experiment C CH₄ concentrations

		0	150	375
treatment	Bottle number	mmol in HS	mmol in HS	mmol in HS
Natural	C1	0.039	0.039	0.046
Natural	C2	0.043	0.031	0.047
Hematite	C3	0.038	0.030	0.046
Hematite	C4	0.048	0.034	0.047
BES+Hematite	C5	0.042	0.041	0.045
BES+Hematite	C6	0.035	0.033	0.044
Molybdate+Hematite	C7	0.038	0.029	0.041
Molybdate+Hematite	C8	0.041	0.032	0.052
Magnetite	C9	0.042	0.032	0.044
Magnetite	C10	0.049	0.030	0.044
Acetylene+Hematite	C11	0.047	0.039	0.048
Acetylene+Hematite	C12	0.041	0.029	0.042
Amorphous iron	C13	0.023	0.032	0.045
Amorphous iron	C14	0.028	0.034	0.045
BES+A. iron	C15	0.027	0.027	0.037
BES+A. iron	C16	0.030	0.025	0.035
Molybdate+A. iron	C17	0.031	0.026	0.034
Molybdate+A. iron	C18	0.034	0.035	0.042
Amorphous iron	C19	0.027	0.021	0.039
Amorphous iron	C20	0.036	0.024	0.047
Acetylene+A. iron	C21	0.076	0.050	0.071
Acetylene+A. iron	C22	0.034	0.025	0.039
AQDS+A. iron	C23	0.032	0.028	0.044
AQDS+A. iron	C24	0.037	0.031	0.045

Dead BES+Hematite	C27	0.037	0.030	0.047
Dead BES+Hematite	C28	0.033	0.028	0.021
Dead Acetylene+Hematite	C29	0.040	0.017	0.024
Dead Acetylene+Hematite	C30	0.033	0.019	0.036
Dead Molybdate+A. iron+Hematite	C31	0.032	0.024	0.028
Dead Molybdate+A. iron+Hematite	C32	0.032	0.026	0.040
Dead Amorphous iron	C33	0.037	0.020	0.039
Dead Amorphous iron	C34	0.039	0.023	0.035
Dead AQDS+A. iron	C35	0.031	0.034	0.046
Dead AQDS+A. iron	C36	0.040	0.029	0.038
Dead Acetylene+A. iron	C25	0.030	0.022	0.046
Dead Acetylene+A. iron	C26	0.029	0.024	0.035
Hematite	C37	0.035	0.027	0.040
Natural	C38	0.035	0.024	0.043

Fe(II) concentration during the one year experiment are presented in Figure 1S, divided to natural and iron oxides (Fig. 1SA), hematite and inhibitors added (Fig.1SB), and amorphous iron and inhibitors added (Fig. 1SC). Fe(II) initial concentration in bottles which were set up from slurry incubation bottle 1 (see table 7) was $\sim 100 \mu\text{M}$, in bottles from slurry incubation bottle 2 $\sim 130 \mu\text{M}$, in bottles from slurry incubation bottle 3 $\sim 110 \mu\text{M}$, and in bottles from slurry incubation bottle 4 $\sim 75 \mu\text{M}$. Except BES added bottles (both with hematite and amorphous iron), all bottles didn't have a clear trend. All bottles showed up to $20 \mu\text{M}$ variation, similar or less than their autoclaved parallel treatment. Fe(II) concentration in autoclaved bottles with amorphous iron increased up to $85 \mu\text{M}$ in the first 21 days, then decreased gradually to final concentration of $\sim 100 \mu\text{M}$. Fe(II) concentration in autoclaved bottles with hematite decreased in $20 \mu\text{M}$ in the first 7 days, then kept on a stable value with $10 \mu\text{M}$ variation. Fe(II) concentration in bottles containing BES increase consistently in both bottles containing hematite and amorphous iron. In bottles containing hematite, Fe(II) concentration increase from $\sim 100 \mu\text{M}$ to $\sim 130 \mu\text{M}$, and in bottles containing amorphous iron from $\sim 140 \mu\text{M}$ to $\sim 210 \mu\text{M}$.

Figure 1S: Experiment C Fe(II) concentrations. A-Natural and iron oxides added bottles. B-Bottles containing hematite and inhibitors. C-Bottles containing amorphous iron and inhibitors.

Methane initial amounts in HS were between 0.023 mmol to 0.049 (Fig. 2S). The amounts stayed stable or increased in all live bottles. Bottles containing amorphous iron with no inhibitor showed the largest increase of 0.012 to 0.022 mmol in HS. Dead control bottles showed different trends, some increased in up to 0.016 mmol and some decreased in down to 0.016 mmol, with no consistent between duplicates.

Figure 2S: Experiment C Methane amounts in HS. A-Natural and iron oxides added bottles. B-Bottles containing hematite and inhibitors. C-Bottles containing amorphous iron and inhibitors.

DIC initial concentration (Fig. 3SA, 3SC, 3SE) in bottles which were set up from slurry incubation bottle 1 (see table 7) was ~3.2 mM, in bottles from slurry incubation bottle

2 ~4 mM, in bottles from slurry incubation bottle 3 ~3.7 mM, and in bottles from slurry incubation bottle 4 ~6.3 mM. BES added bottles (both with hematite and amorphous iron) showed the biggest increase in DIC concentration. Concentrations in bottles with BES and hematite increased in ~2 mM, to final concentration of ~5.2 mM, and bottles with BES and amorphous iron increased in ~2.75 mM, to final concentration of ~6.8 mM. DIC concentrations in live bottles with amorphous iron increased in ~1.5 mM, to a final concentration of ~5.7 mM, compare to autoclaved bottles with same treatment, which the concentrations increased in ~1.1 mM (from ~6.3 mM to ~7.4 mM). DIC concentrations in live bottles with amorphous iron and molybdate increased in ~1.5 mM, to a final concentration of ~5.6 mM, compare to autoclaved bottles with molybdate, amorphous iron and hematite, which the concentrations decreased in 0.9 mM (from ~6.2 mM to ~5.3 mM). DIC concentrations in live bottles with amorphous iron and AQDS increased in ~1.4 mM, to a final concentration of ~5.1 mM, compare to autoclaved bottles with same treatment, which the concentrations decreased in 0.4 mM and 1.1 mM (from ~6.4 mM to ~6 mM and ~5.3 mM). DIC concentrations in live bottles with amorphous iron and acetylene increased in 1.4 mM and 1.7 mM, to a final concentration of ~5 mM and 5.5 mM, compare to autoclaved bottles with same treatment, which the concentrations increased in ~1.4 mM (from ~6.25 mM to ~7.6 mM). All other bottles, including natural, hematite, hematite and inhibitors (beside BES) and magnetite added bottles shows 0.7 to 1 mM increase, compare to autoclaved bottles with same treatment, which showed 0.3 mM decrease.

The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ initial values (Fig. 3SB, 3SD, 3SF) in bottles which were set up from slurry incubation bottle 1 (see table 7) was ~-10‰, in bottles from slurry incubation bottle 2 ~-11.7‰, in bottles from slurry incubation bottle 3 ~-11.5‰, and in bottles from slurry incubation bottle 4 ~-7.3‰. Except BES added bottles (both with hematite and amorphous iron), all bottles kept a stable $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values, with up to 1‰ variation along a full year, similar or less than their autoclaved parallel bottle. BES added bottles showed 8‰ to 9.5‰ decrease in $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values, while autoclaved BES added bottles showed only 0.3‰ decreased (Fig. 3SD, 3SF).

Figure 3S: DIC concentration and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values of experiment C. A- DIC concentrations of natural and the bottles containing different iron oxides. B- $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values of natural and bottles containing different iron oxides. C-DIC concentrations of bottles containing hematite and bottles containing hematite with different inhibitors. D- $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values of bottles containing hematite and bottles containing hematite with different inhibitors. E-DIC concentrations of bottles containing amorphous iron and bottles containing amorphous iron with different inhibitors. F- $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values of bottles containing amorphous iron and bottles containing amorphous iron with different inhibitors.

7.4 Experiment D data tables

Table 16S: Experiment D Fe(II) concentrations

	μM								
days	0	6	21	47	104	180	215	266	361
treatment									
Natural	2.5	2.6	1.6	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.5	0.7	0.7
Natural	2.3	2.5	0.8	0.2	0.3	0.1	0.5	3.1	3.1
Hemetite	1.5	1.3	0.4	0.1	0.3	12.0	13.7	15.7	15.7
Hemetite	2.5	3.0	1.4	1.2	0.4	0.1	0.3	1.0	1.0
Amorphus	3.1	66.7	80.9	96.1	199.3	434.3	425.6	404.6	278.3
Amorphus	1.3	59.5	93.1	81.8	133.4	248.4	262.3	289.1	278.6
Hemetite+Molybdate	1.5	10.1	15.1	16.0	10.0	7.5	1.3	1.4	1.3
Hemetite+Molybdate	1.8	9.5	14.3	14.9	10.2	3.8	2.5	1.6	1.6
Dead+Hemetite	6.5	20.4	22.7	24.1	31.1	37.5	37.2	36.8	36.2
Dead+A. iron	6.7	164.5	158.4	154.5	150.6	186.5	182.1	102.5	96.1

Table 17S: Experiment D DIC concentrations

	mM						
days	0	47	104	180	215	266	361
treatment							
Natural	12.8	14.8	18.5	19.3	19.9	21.5	21.5
Natural	11.7	13.5	16.6	17.9	18.7	20.6	21.4
Hemetite	12.0	15.2	20.9	20.9	21.7	23.8	24.4
Hemetite	12.0	13.4	16.1	17.6	18.9	20.6	21.7
Amorphus	12.5	15.1	22.0	22.5	22.6	24.6	24.7
Amorphus	12.4	12.1	15.9	17.8	19.0	20.9	23.5
Hemetite+Molybdate	10.8	12.0	14.4	15.4	16.2	17.3	19.6
Hemetite+Molybdate	11.9	12.5	14.3	14.8	15.7	16.5	18.7
Dead+Hemetite	10.5	9.7	10.8	10.5	11.0	11.2	12.3
Dead+Amorphus	10.1	11.7	12.9	12.0	13.2	13.2	13.4

Table 18S: Experiment D $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ concentrations

	‰						
days	0	47	104	180	215	266	361
treatment							
Natural	-6.8	-6.6	-8.6	-4.2	-0.2	7.1	24.7
Natural	-7.1	-4.7	-5.6	-7.6	-8.0	-8.3	-2.2
Hemetite	-7.3	-8.9	-11.8	-1.8	2.1	8.4	21.7
Hemetite	-7.3	-4.4	-4.3	-5.8	-6.3	-5.9	0.0
Amorphus	-7.1	-10.6	-13.9	-11.0	-8.9	-4.1	8.0
Amorphus	-7.5	-7.9	-9.6	-10.5	-10.9	-9.7	-7.6
Hemetite+Molybdate	-6.9	-5.4	-5.0	-3.3	-2.8	-0.8	-0.2
Hemetite+Molybdate	-7.4	-5.0	-4.2	-1.5	-0.7	1.5	3.0
Dead+Hemetite	-6.9	-5.6	-6.4	-7.0	-7.0	-6.9	-4.3
Dead+Amorphus	-6.0	-6.4	-7.2	-6.9	-7.6	-7.6	-6.1

Table 19S: Experiment D CH₄ concentrations

	mmol in HS	mmol in HS	mmol in HS
days	0	211	279
treatment	initial value according to dead bottles		
Natural	0.11	0.20	0.16
Natural	0.11	0.14	0.10
Hematite	0.11	0.23	0.18
Hematite	0.11	0.08	0.09
Amorphous	0.11	0.17	0.13
Amorphous	0.11	0.11	0.09
Hematite+Molybdate	0.11	0.18	0.14
Hematite+Molybdate	0.11	0.15	0.13
Dead+Hematite	0.11	0.11	0.11
Dead+A. iron	0.11	0.11	0.09

Table 20S: Experiment D SO₄ concentrations

	mM						
days	0	47	104	180	215	266	361
treatment							
Natural	3.2	2.2	1.3	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.0
Natural	4.0	3.3	2.6	1.2	1.0	0.6	0.2
Hematite	4.1	1.9	0.4	0.1	0.1	0.4	0.3
Hematite	4.2	3.3	2.4	1.1	0.8	0.4	0.0
Amorphous	4.6	2.2	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0
Amorphous	4.5	3.7	2.8	1.8	1.4	1.1	0.1
Hematite+Molybdate	4.5	4.1	3.8	3.3	2.9	2.7	1.5
Hematite+Molybdate	5.3	4.6	4.3	4.1	3.5	3.4	2.3
Dead+Hematite	4.4	4.0	4.0	4.7	4.7	4.6	4.4
Dead+A. iron	6.1	4.6	4.8	5.0	5.0	5.1	3.9

Table 21S: Experiment D sulfide concentrations

	uM	μM	μM	μM	μM	μM	μM	μM	μM
days	0	6	21	47	104	180	215	266	361
treatment									
Natural	33.8	41.2	159.4	259.6	597.9	376.1	375.7	299.5	64.3
Natural	33.3	41.2	112.8	213.2	363.8	406.3	418.3	421.9	418.8
Hematite	40.9	59.4	215.4	202.9	270.4	15.2	12.0	13.0	16.2
Hematite	43.8	31.6	56.7	137.1	273.4	233.5	145.2	73.0	52.1
Amorphous	31.7	1.1	1.1	1.5	2.4	2.0	0.5	0.9	1.7
Amorphous	60.7	1.5	0.9	0.9	1.1	1.3	0.4	0.2	1.1
Hematite+Molybdate	54.9	21.4	13.4	11.7	15.0	32.2	46.4	63.1	62.8
Hematite+Molybdate	38.9	20.8	15.0	13.7	16.7	18.1	29.5	57.0	26.5
Dead+Hematite	150.4	66.3	33.4	16.3	15.1	7.4	6.8	5.3	6.7
Dead+A. iron	137.4	4.8	3.8	2.9	4.0	3.8	1.8	2.0	2.4

7.5 Experiment E data tables

Table 22S: Experiment E Fe(II) concentrations

	μM						
days	0	5	13	26	81	153	248
treatment							
Natural	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.5	2.2	2.8
Natural	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.5	2.2	3.6
Natural	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.7	0.2	2.1	3.2
Natural	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.5	2.2	3.4
Molybdate	0.6	0.9	1.4	1.5	2.9	3.1	4.2
Molybdate	0.6	1.0	1.0	1.5	2.7	3.0	3.7
Hematite	0.6	0.8	0.7	1.2	1.7	3.1	4.2
Hematite	0.8	0.7	0.7	1.1	1.7	2.7	4.3
Magnetite	0.6	1.4	1.8	2.1	3.0	4.2	5.6
Magnetite	0.6	1.5	1.7	2.0	3.0	4.7	5.7
Magnetite+BES	0.6	2.1	3.1	5.1	9.3	13.6	22.9
Magnetite+BES	0.8	2.4	3.5	4.7	8.1	14.4	25.7
Magnetite+Molybdate	0.8	1.7	2.0	2.4	3.6	4.8	6.6
Magnetite+Molybdate	0.7	1.6	1.9	2.3	3.5	4.9	6.3
Amorphous iron	0.7	12.9	15.2	17.1	26.3	32.9	44.6
Amorphous iron	0.7	11.9	14.3	16.6	26.2	32.4	43.5
Dead+A. iron	4.6	48.7	46.1	41.9	44.8	36.9	40.1
Dead+Magnetite	3.5	4.1	4.4	4.6	5.5	5.5	5.4
Dead+Magnetite+BES	3.7	3.8	4.4	4.9	6.8	8.1	10.9

Table 23S: Experiment E DIC concentrations

	mM	mM	mM	mM	mM
days	0	26	81	153	248
treatment					
Natural	9.5	10.0	10.2	10.8	11.3
Natural	9.6	9.5	10.3	10.9	11.3
Natural	9.9	9.7	10.3	11.3	11.3
Natural	9.7	10.1	10.1	11.2	11.5
Molybdate	10.0	10.0	10.4	10.7	11.1
Molybdate	10.0	9.8	9.9	10.6	10.9
Hematite	9.3	9.8	10.4	11.0	11.5
Hematite	9.8	9.8	10.6	11.0	11.4
Magnetite	9.9	9.9	10.5	11.2	11.9
Magnetite	10.0	9.7	10.5	11.2	11.9
Magnetite+BES	10.1	9.4	10.7	11.2	11.6
Magnetite+BES	10.3	10.1	11.5	12.2	12.5
Magnetite+Molybdate	10.2	9.8	10.4	11.2	11.6
Magnetite+Molybdate	10.0	9.7	10.4	11.2	11.6
Amorpous iron	9.9	8.9	9.3	10.0	10.9
Amorpous iron	10.0	8.6	9.1	10.0	10.7
Dead+A. iron	8.1	9.4	9.7	10.1	10.1
Dead+Magnetite	7.9	7.4	7.8	8.3	8.7
Dead+Magnetite+BES	8.4	7.2	7.6	8.1	8.0

Table 24S: Experiment E $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ concentrations

	‰	‰	‰	‰	‰
days	0	26	81	153	248
treatment					
Natural	-14.7	-14.4	-12.3	-8.1	-0.3
Natural	-14.8	-14.1	-11.1	-6.9	1.3
Natural	-14.8	-14.4	-11.3	-7.0	1.2
Natural	-14.8	-14.2	-13.8	-7.0	1.6
Molybdate	-14.6	-14.3	-11.4	-13.8	-13.1
Molybdate	-14.6	-14.3	-13.6	-13.6	-12.9
Hematite	-14.7	-14.4	-13.7	-10.5	-2.8
Hematite	-14.6	-14.3	-13.8	-11.8	-4.7
Magnetite	-14.5	-14.7	-14.3	-14.2	-13.5
Magnetite	-14.6	-14.5	-14.3	-14.2	-12.9
Magnetite+BES	-14.6	-15.3	-15.6	-15.9	-16.3
Magnetite+BES	-14.5	-16.2	-19.7	-19.9	-19.9
Magnetite+Molybdate	-14.5	-14.6	-13.7	-12.9	-12.5
Magnetite+Molybdate	-14.4	-14.4	-13.7	-12.9	-11.9
Amorphous iron	-14.4	-14.4	-14.1	-14.1	-14.2
Amorphous iron	-14.4	-14.4	-13.9	-14.0	-14.1
Dead+A. iron	-12.8	-14.6	-14.0	-14.2	-14.0
Dead+Magnetite	-12.8	-12.8	-11.8	-12.2	-12.0
Dead+Magnetite+BES	-13.1	-12.7	-12.2	-12.1	-11.7

Table 25S: Experiment E sulfide concentrations

	μM						
days	0	5	13	26	81	153	248
treatment							
Natural	27.4	42.0	44.7	38.4	30.7	24.5	19.0
Natural	27.8	40.3	45.3	41.3	29.6	24.0	22.4
Natural	18.8	38.4	45.5	41.2	31.1	25.8	21.8
Natural	25.7	41.1	44.3	42.0	30.6	25.1	22.0
Molybdate	20.1	20.4	14.9	18.4	14.3	10.2	12.8
Molybdate	18.5	18.0	19.6	18.9	11.3	11.0	11.1
Hematite	18.0	27.9	28.1	26.9	19.3	18.8	19.7
Hematite	14.4	26.4	25.1	22.5	15.0	18.2	19.8
Magnetite	12.0	12.4	8.9	10.2	9.3	9.2	12.6
Magnetite	10.3	12.2	11.5	10.8	9.8	8.9	12.0
Magnetite+BES	10.8	7.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Magnetite+BES	10.5	7.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Magnetite+Molybdate	9.0	11.0	11.1	10.8	9.3	11.4	10.8
Magnetite+Molybdate	8.2	12.0	10.5	11.2	10.6	9.5	12.0
Amorphous iron	7.4	1.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Amorphous iron	7.4	1.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Dead+A. iron	82.2	4.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Dead+Magnetite	83.4	32.8	23.8	26.3	20.6	15.0	20.6
Dead+Magnetite+BES	87.1	14.5	12.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

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חיזור ברזל בסדימנטים של מדף היבשת העמוק בים התיכון ואסטואר נחל הירקון

מאת עומר יורשנסקי
עבודת גמר לתואר "מגיסטר"
אוניברסיטת בן-גוריון בנגב
2020

תקציר

תחמוצות ברזל בעלות תפקיד מפתח בשרשרת הנשימה הבקטריאלית האנאירובית של חומר אורגני בסדימנטים, אשר מצומדת לקבלי אלקטרונים לפי הרווח האנרגטי המופק מהם. לאחרונה, מחקרים הראו כי תהליכים מיקרוביאליים הכוללים קבלי אלקטרונים שונים יכולים להתקיים במקביל באותו אזור. בנוסף, בסדימנטים ימיים רבים, כולל משקעי מדף יבשתי של דרום מזרח הים התיכון אותם חקרתי במחקרי, נצפה חיזור ברזל מיקרוביאלי מפתיע הרבה מתחת לאזור החיזור אשר הוא מצופה להימצא בו, בעומק המתאנוגנזה. תופעה זו מאתגרת את הבנתנו על מחזורי הברזל ואלמנטים בסיסיים נוספים. מטרת המחקר הייתה לחקור את המנגנונים ואת הקשר ליסודות נוספים של תהליך חיזור הברזל בסדימנטים הנשלטים ע"י דיפוזיה. התמקדתי בשני אזורים: (1) הגבול העליון של אזור המתאנוגנזה, המכונה SMTZ, שם חמצון מתאן אנאירובי יחד עם חיזור סולפט הוא התהליך העיקרי. (2) אזור המתאנוגנזה העמוק, בו פרופילים ימיים רבים מראים עלייה משמעותית בברזל מומס בלתי מוסברת יחד עם ירידה בריכוז המתאן. באזור העליון, בדקתי את ההשפעה של נוכחות תחמוצות ברזל על תהליכי החמצון האנאירובי של מתאן (AOM) המצומד לחיזור סולפט ושל מתאנוגנזה.

המחקר נערך בשתי סביבות ימיות, השונות בתכולת הפחמן האורגני שלהן: מדף היבשתי האוליגוטרופי של דרום מזרח הים התיכון, ואסטואר הירקון העשיר בחומר אורגני. פרופילים גאוכימיים בוצעו בשתי הסביבות, וזוהו עומקי ה-SMTZ ומיקומי חיזור הברזל העמוק הבלתי מוסבר. בנוסף, הועמדו חמישה ניסויי אינקובציה: שלושה ניסויים מהים התיכון (אחד מסדימנטים מאזור ה-SMTZ ושניים מתוך אזור חיזור הברזל העמוק), ושני ניסויים מאסטואר הירקון (אחד מסדימנטים רדודים עם ריכוז סולפט גבוה ואחד מסדימנטים עמוקים המדולדלים בסולפט). בקבוקי האינקובציה הכילו סדימנטים מהעומק והמיקום הרצוי, יחד עם תחמוצות ברזל שונות, מתאן מסומן ב- ^{13}C , ומעקבים לתהליכים שונים. הניסויים נדגמו למומסים של ברזל(II), סולפיד, סולפט, מתאן, פחמן אי אורגני (DIC) ול- $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ במשך 9-18 חודשים, על מנת לבחון את השפעת הטיפול השונים על הפרמטרים הגיאוכימיים של מי החללים.

תוצאות המחקר שלי הראו שחיזור ברזל עמוק התרחש בכל הסביבות שנחקרו, גם אם לא נצפו באופן טבעי בפרופילים הגיאוכימיים. בנוסף, AOM התרחש בסדימנטים מאזור ה-SMTZ של הים התיכון, ובסדימנטים רדודים ועמוקים של אסטואר הירקון. ה-AOM הנצפה במחקר זה נובע מחיזור סולפט, אפילו בריכוזי סולפט נמוכים. AOM לא נצפה בסדימנטים מאזור חיזור הברזל העמוק מהים התיכון, כנראה בגלל היעדר סולפט באזור זה, שנגרם ממרחק וזמן דיפוזיה ארוך, המונע מסולפט להגיע לאזור עמוק זה ולאפשר את התהליך. במקום AOM, ניסויי האינקובציה הראו כי נוכחות תחמוצות ברזל מעכבת את המתאנוגנזה הטבעית המתרחשת באזור זה, וגם את ה-AOM עם סולפט בניסויים אחרים. קצב חיזור הסולפט הוא הגורם העיקרי השולט בכל התהליכים האחרים באסטואר הירקון (חיזור ברזל, מתאנוגנזה ו-AOM), ורק כאשר ריכוז הסולפט או קצב חיזור הסולפט ירד משמעותית, נצפו התהליכים האחרים בסדימנטים.

אוניברסיטת בן-גוריון בנגב

הפקולטה למדעי הטבע

המחלקה למדעי הגיאולוגיה והסביבה

חיזור ברזל בסדימנטים של מדף היבשת העמוק בים

התיכון ואסטואר נחל הירקון

חיבור לשם קבלת התואר "מגיסטר" בפקולטה למדעי הטבע

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ינואר 2020

טבת תש"פ